

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

Constructive metabolic processes for material flows in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 3.3

URBAN METABOLISM STRATEGY: FINAL REPORT

Due date of deliverable: 31/05/2022

Actual submission date: 31/05/2022

Start date of project: 01/06/2019 Duration (36 Months)

Dissemination Level: Public ✓

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.*

DELIVERABLE

Work Package	WP3
Deliverable	D3.3 Urban Metabolism Strategy Final Report
Tasks	Task 3.4 Environmental Impact Assessment [M24-M36]
Document Name	Urban Metabolism Strategy: Final Report
Due Date	M36: 31 May 2022
Submission Date	M36: 31 May 2022
Dissemination Level	P-Public
Deliverable Lead	Metabolic Institute (MET)
Author(s)	Antoine Coudard, Elodie Chatel, Apurva Singh, Liz Corbin, Savanna Browne-Wilkinson, Frenzi Ritter, Tamara Streefland, Vicky Miles, Soumya Sood, Pilar Bolumburu, Alysia Garmulewicz, Charlene Smith
Point of Contact	Apurva Singh, apurva@metabolic.nl
Reviewers	Stefano Bocconi (Waag), Marta Savoldelli (OpenDot)
Status	Final
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This report presents the methodology and results of WP3, Task 3.4 Environmental Impact Assessment within the REFLOW project. Its aims to communicate the outcomes of each pilot city's circular interventions and strategies -including an environmental impact assessments, and a discussion on these interventions may affect the urban metabolism of each of the Pilot Cities.
Keywords	Environmental impact assessment; Urban metabolism; Impact hotspots; Circular strategies.
Statement of Originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author(s)	Organization	Description
D3.3 v0.1	29/04/22	Antoine Coudard (MET), Elodie Chatel (MET), Apurva Singh (MET), Liz Corbin (MET), Savanna Browne-Wilkinson (MET), Frenzi Ritter (MET), Martijn Kamps (MET), Tamara Streefland (MET), Vicky Miles (MET), Soumya Sood (MET), Pilar Bolumburu (MAT), Alysia Garmulewicz (MAT), Charlene Smith (MAT)	MET, MATERIOM	First draft
D3.3 v0.2	24/05/22	Antoine Coudard, Elodie Chatel, Apurva Singh, Liz Corbin, Savanna Browne-Wilkinson, Frenzi Ritter, Martijn Kamps, Tamara Streefland, Vicky Miles, Soumya Sood, Pilar Bolumburu, Alysia Garmulewicz, Charlene Smith	MET, MATERIOM	Change by partners
D7.1 v1.0	31/05/22	Antoine Coudard (MET), Elodie Chatel (MET), Apurva Singh (MET), Liz Corbin (MET), Savanna Browne-Wilkinson (MET), Frenzi Ritter (MET), Martijn Kamps (MET), Tamara Streefland (MET)	MET, MATERIOM	Final version by the consortium to be submitted to the EC.

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the REFLOW project consortium under EC grant agreement number 820937 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

INDEX

List of abbreviations	6
List of figures	7
List of tables	8
Definitions and keywords	9
1. Introduction	13
2. Amsterdam pilot	19
Introduction	19
Intervention 1: The Swapshop	20
Intervention 2: Isolation gowns	29
3. Berlin pilot	37
Introduction	37
Intervention: Wastewater Heat Radar	38
4. Cluj pilot	45
Introduction	45
Intervention: Retrofit Kit	46
5. Milan pilot	52
Introduction	52
Intervention: Foody Zero Waste	53
6. Paris pilot	63
Introduction	63
Intervention: Dimension-use	64
7. Vejle pilot	72
Introduction	72
Intervention 1: REMA1000	73
Intervention 2: Plastic in Healthcare	80
8. Conclusion	87
References	91
Appendix	94

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations:

BAU: Business-as-usual
CE: Circular economy
COP: Coefficient of performance
DEHP: Bi(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate
EEA: European Economic Area
EFA: Energy flow analysis
EOL: End-of-life
EPR: Extended producer responsibility
EU: European Union
EVA: Ethylene-vinyl acetate
GHG: Greenhouse gases
HDPE: High-density polyethylene
JRC: Joint research centre
KPI: Key performance indicator
LCA: Life-cycle assessment
LDPE: Low-density polyethylene
LED: Light-emitting diode
MDF: Medium density fibreboard
MFA: Material flow analysis
OSB: Oriented strand board
PE: Polyethylene
PET: Polyethylene terephthalate
POD: Point of consumption
PP: Polypropylene
PS: Polystyrene
PVC: Polyvinyl chloride
REFLOW OS: REFLOW operating system
RFID: Radio-frequency identification
SME: Small and medium-sized enterprise
SROI: Social return on investment
WP: Work package

Units:

Mass:

kg: kilogram
tonne: 1 metric tonne
ktonne: Thousand metric tonnes
Mtonne: Million metric tonne

Environmental emissions:

tonne CO₂-eq: 1 tonne of carbon dioxide-equivalent of greenhouse gases
tonne 1,4 DCB-eq: 1 tonne of dichlorobenzene-equivalent

Energy:

kW: kilowatt
kWh: kilowatt hour
MWh: Megawatt hour
GWh: Gigawatt hour

Volume

m³ : cubic metre

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1** Visual reading guide of this document
- Figure 2** The REFLOW framework
- Figure 3** Amsterdam's first Swapshop location located on Haarlemmerdijk
- Figure 4** Life-cycle stages of the Swapshop
- Figure 5** Raw material use comparison for the Swapshop intervention
- Figure 6** GHG emissions comparison for the Swapshop intervention
- Figure 7** The Circular Isolation Gown developed by the Amsterdam pilot
- Figure 8** Life-cycle stages of the Isolation Gowns use case
- Figure 9** Raw material use comparison for the Isolation Gowns intervention
- Figure 10** GHG emissions comparison for the Isolation Gowns intervention
- Figure 11** The Waste Water Heat Radar Main View
- Figure 12** Open Data Dashboard
- Figure 13** Conceptual model of the heat capacity of heat pumps
- Figure 14** GHG emissions comparison for wastewater heat
- Figure 15** Energy use monitoring app
- Figure 16** Electricity mix in Cluj-Napoca
- Figure 17** Electricity consumption comparison for the Cluj-Napoca pilot
- Figure 18** GHG emissions comparison for the Cluj-Napoca pilot
- Figure 19** Telegram BOT interacting between wholesalers and organisations
- Figure 20** Life-cycle stages of the Foody Zero Waste intervention
- Figure 21** Food saved comparison for the Foody Zero Waste intervention
- Figure 22** GHG emissions avoided for the Foody Zero Waste intervention
- Figure 23** Dimension-use system used during the use case
- Figure 24** Wood collected and modular constructions
- Figure 25** Life-cycle stages of the REFLOW intervention
- Figure 26** Raw material use comparison for the Dimension-use intervention
- Figure 27** GHG emissions comparison for the Dimension-use intervention
- Figure 28** Life-cycle stages of the REMA 1000 use case
- Figure 29** Plastic waste comparison for REMA 1000
- Figure 30** GHG emissions comparison for REMA 1000
- Figure 31** Life-cycle stages of the Sofiegården use case
- Figure 32** Plastic waste comparison for Sofiegården
- Figure 33** GHG emissions comparison for Sofiegården

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1	CO ₂ -eq., water, and land use impacts for different fibres
Table 2	CO ₂ -eq impacts textile incineration
Table 3	Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline, the intervention, and the scaled intervention for the Swapshop intervention
Table 4	Life-Cycle impacts of polypropylene isolation gowns
Table 5	Life-Cycle impacts of cotton isolation gowns
Table 6	Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline, the intervention, and the scaled intervention for the Isolation Gowns intervention
Table 7	Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline, the intervention, and the scaled intervention for the Cluj-Napoca pilot
Table 8	Environmental impacts of production of the baseline scenario retrieved from RVIM for the Foody Zero Waste intervention
Table 9	Environmental impacts of production of the intervention retrieved from RVIM for the Foody Zero Waste intervention
Table 10	Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline and the intervention for the Foody Zero Waste intervention
Table 11	Environmental impacts of the production stage of different wood products
Table 12	Waste routes and environmental impacts of wood products' waste treatment
Table 13	Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline and the intervention of the Dimension-use intervention
Table 14	Life-cycle impacts of plastics
Table 15	Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline and the intervention of the REMA 1000 use case
Table 16	Environmental impacts of plastic products end-of-life treatments
Table 17	Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline and the intervention for the Plastic in Healthcare intervention
Table 18	GHG emissions of cotton mechanical recycling based on the Dutch Energy Grid
Table 19	Products recovered by RECUP during the test period

DEFINITIONS AND KEYWORDS

Bio-based material	A material that is partially, or entirely made of biomass.
Biodegradable materials	A material which microorganisms can break down into natural elements (i.e. water, biomass, etc.).
By-product	A material or substance created when processing or manufacturing something else.
Capacity building	The process by which individuals and organisations obtain, improve, and retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment and other resources needed to do their jobs competently or to a greater capacity.
Circular city	A circular city is a city where the circular economy principles are implemented and result in a resilient system that facilitates new kinds of social, environmental, technological, and economic activities. Examples of which can be the strengthening of competitiveness and the generation of employment.
Circular Economy (CE)	A circular economy is an alternative to a dominant linear industrial model of design, produce, purchase, consume and dispose. A circular model aims to redefine growth and positive societal impacts. It entails a transition from using finite energy and material resources, to using renewable ones (designing the concept of-waste out of the system). A systemic approach is necessary, as well as a deep transformation of habits and behaviour: from the way we design, produce, consume, purchase, and dispose to how we value existing, or even abundant, resources present in the local environments. Although starting from different materials in REFLOW, the focus of the circular economy gradually extends beyond these issues related to material management and covers other aspects such as the social impact, technological aspects, and the evolution of urban governance structures.
Co-creation	Co-creation is a bottom-up and design driven approach that's fundamental to build a common and supported understanding of new routes and futures through all layers of society.
Design for disassembly	Design principle that calls for the end-of-life options of how the product, components and materials can be deconstructed.

Design for flexibility	A design principle most commonly applied in building design and construction that calls for use of interstitial space, programmed soft space, shell space, expansion capacity, demountable partitions, and mobile or modular furnishings.
Food surplus	Edible food produced in a quantity exceeding the needs of the commercial food sector.
Food waste	Food intended for human consumption that is discarded at any point of the value chain. It can be due to spoilage, oversupply, or individual consumer/eating habits.
End-of-life	The life cycle stage during which a product no longer has value to its original owner and is then disposed of.
Environmental impact assessment	Environmental impact assessment is a process of evaluating the environmental impacts of a material, product, or any type of proposed project or development, taking into account its entire life-cycle. It also considers the inter-related socio-economic, cultural, and human-health impacts, both beneficial and adverse.
Iterative design	Iterative design is a design methodology based on continual improvement of a concept, prototype, design or product. In Reflow, iterative design will be conceived with an agile structure enabling continuous improvements and adjustments of the local pilot projects in a collaborative manner.
Key Performance Indicator	Key performance indicators (KPIs) refer to a set of quantifiable measurements used to gauge overall long-term performance. KPIs are used not only to measure economic benefits (e.g., value creation and savings by reducing the purchase of primary raw materials), but also environmental benefits (e.g., impact reduction), and social benefits (e.g., job creation).
Life cycle thinking	Approach of accounting for economic, environmental and social impacts across all stages of a product or services life cycle.
Life cycle	All of the stages that a product goes through in its lifetime: raw material extraction, processing, manufacturing, use, end-of-life and transportation.
Material flow	The quantity and rate at which materials move through a system (i.e. city, company, etc.).
Material passport	A cryptographically signed trace of all the events a resource has gone through (a resource's history), including actors and other resources present in those events.
Pilot	A small-scale test or experiment in the preparation for bigger activities at a later stage.

Raw materials	Crude or virgin materials that are used in product manufacturing or processing.
Recovery	Process of extracting material, energy or water from the waste stream for reuse or recycling.
Recycling	The collection, sorting and processing of disposed materials for use in another manufacturing process.
REFLOW OS	An online exchange platform acting as a Value-Based Network platform for recycled resources. REFLOW OS has the ambition to create a marketplace to facilitate exchanges of materials, help locate and track materials and resources, and facilitate exchange through smart contracts.
Regenerative city	A regenerative city moves beyond sustainability, and develops a restorative, mutually beneficial relationship with the natural and social systems that sustain it. In Reflow, the road to generative urban development will be achieved through the attention to the social, environmental, technological and economic dimensions.
Regenerative economy	An approach in which products and services replenish their own sources of energy, water and materials in a closed-loop system.
Remanufacturing	Process of recovery, disassembly, repair and sanitising components or parts for resale and reuse.
Renewable resources	Materials, energy and water sources that replenish themselves after human extraction within a finite amount of time.
Resource efficiency	A percentage of the total resources consumed that make up the final product or service.
Reuse	Using a product or material again, either for the same or an alternative function.
Scaling	A way to boost learning and transferability via feedback loops that contribute to wider scale adoption, promoting outputs and outcomes beyond the immediate ecosystem.
Stakeholder	A group, organisation, member, individual or system that affects or can be affected by an organisation's actions.

Systems thinking	Systems thinking is the ability or skill to perform problem solving in complex systems. A system is an entity with interrelated and interdependent parts; it is defined by its boundaries and is more than the sum of its parts (subsystem). Changing one part of the system affects other parts and the whole system, with predictable patterns of behaviour. Furthermore, the individuals working as part of a system are components as well, therefore contributing to its outcome.
Use case	Describes a series of events and interactions between a user and a system, in order to produce a result of value.
Urban Metabolism	Urban metabolism is a model that examines material and energy flows within cities as complex systems, as various social, environmental, economic governance and technological factors shape them.
Value proposition	A value proposition is a promise of value to be delivered, communicated, and acknowledged.

1. INTRODUCTION

Introduction to the REFLOW project

About REFLOW

REFLOW is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, REFLOW uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualise, and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge, and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximise multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project provides best practices aligning market and government needs in order to create favourable conditions for the public and private sector to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. REFLOW is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris, and Vejle. The project assesses their social, environmental, and economic impact by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

REFLOW vision

A circular and regenerative city in REFLOW represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to **social, environmental, and economic impact**. It is a system where **technology** is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change, where the urban system ensures and supports resilience of social and ecological systems, where **governance** is collaborative and inclusive, where **knowledge** is shared, and where **stakeholders** are active and involved.

Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable

A primary objective of WP 3 is to assess the environmental performance of the interventions and solutions established by each pilot city, translating the results in ways that support the pilot teams for the future development and evolution of their circular strategies after the project ends. The results of this process are therefore encapsulated within this deliverable's main objectives, which are to, 1) perform an environmental impact assessments of the pilots' interventions that had a **direct environmental impact** on their urban metabolism, and 2) provide an articulation of what these environmental benefits may be once their interventions are scaled at **city-scale**. The main aim of this task (T3.4) and this deliverable is therefore to **evaluate the chosen circular strategies** on their environmental impacts for each of the six pilot cities involved (Amsterdam, Berlin, Milan, Paris, Vejle, and Cluj-Napoca). This deliverable builds upon the material flow analyses (MFAs) and the associated environmental assessment of the pilot's urban metabolism of T3.3 (D3.2) but also on the material development research of T3.2. By calculating the impact of each locally-developed circular intervention using life-cycle assessment thinking and comparing them to the current alternative (BAU baseline), it aims to provide insights into **how these interventions may affect cities' urban metabolism once they scale**. It also aims to describe the different challenges present ahead of these interventions, both in terms of **barriers to market entry** that may impede successful scaling, and in terms of **monitoring resource flows** and their impacts that are necessary for successful implementation.

The overall process undertaken by WP 3 to complete each pilot intervention assessment is documented within this report, as are the results derived. D3.3 Urban Metabolism Strategy: Final Report is divided into three main sections. The reading guide below further elaborates on its structure.

Reading guide

This document is organised into three main sections. The first section, visualised in orange (Figure 1, below) outlines the general scope of the task on which this deliverable reports, the connections with the other deliverables, and describes the overall methodological approach taken in this deliverable. The second section (in green) is composed of the six pilot cities by chapters that describe their circular interventions, the associated environmental impacts, and a reflection on their impacts on each pilot's urban metabolism, should they scale. Finally, the last section (in black) is composed of the conclusion and provide a reflection on the REFLOW interventions analysed in this deliverable, about the challenges faced by circular interventions more generally in their aim of changing positively urban metabolism, and about the lessons learned from monitoring resources flows and their associated environmental impacts within cities.

Included within each pilot chapter are the following sections:

- **Pilot introduction:** A brief introduction to the scope and focus of the pilot in relation to their circular interventions deployed within REFLOW
- **Intervention description:** This section briefly presents the selected solutions developed by the pilots and describes their five-year goal co-developed with the pilots (Deliverable D5.3). The aspects covered in this section for each use case are:
 - The use case performance within REFLOW period (short term)
 - The use case performance as it scales over the next five years (longer term)
- **Methodology:** This section briefly describes the main methodological steps and specific assumptions undertaken, to 1) model the circular flows from the intervention, and 2) evaluate the environmental impacts of the circular intervention assessed.
- **Results:** This section provides the resulting environmental impacts associated with the circular interventions and a comparison to a BAU baseline.
- **Discussion on scaling and resource monitoring:** This section provides an elaboration of what the impacts of the circular solution may be on the urban metabolism should it scale, but also describes the main barriers to market entry that may affect its scaling, and reflects on the challenges of monitoring resource flows.

Figure 1: Visual reading guide of this document.

Methodological Approach of this Deliverable

Selection of interventions for each pilot

Within this deliverable, only a few solutions have been selected per pilot for the environmental impacts analyses (Figure 1). The full list of solutions developed by the REFLOW pilots can be found in Deliverable 1.5. This present deliverable is a continuation of Deliverable 5.3, in which a maximum of two solutions per pilot were evaluated in a longer-term perspective. To determine if the environmental impacts of an intervention were assessed, the following criteria were followed: 1) have a quantitative long-term goal determined within Deliverable 5.3 or have the potential to be scaled based on a scalable factor, 2) have direct environmental impacts, and 3) have enough collected experimental data within the REFLOW project for a meaningful analysis.

The reader should keep in mind certain aspects related to the set of solutions covered in this deliverable: different pilot cities have followed different strategies in developing their solutions. While some cities chose to diversify the solutions and develop prototypes on a smaller scale, others directed their work and resources to fewer, but more large-scale, comprehensive solutions. Therefore, the number of solutions is not in any way indicative of the pilot city efforts, as the solutions vary in scope, depth, and level of progress. Since these interventions are only at the prototype stage, it was not possible to assess in a robust way their indirect environmental impacts. As a result, for this deliverable, the Amsterdam and Vejle pilots had two of their circular interventions assessed, while the Milan, Paris, Cluj-Napoca, and Berlin pilots only had one of their interventions assessed.

Regarding the potential of biobased materials to replace technical flows within the pilots' urban metabolism, the assessment was performed for the following pilots: Vejle, Milan, and Amsterdam. Due to the nature of flows mapped, their current and future activities would be best supported by this type of assessment.

Overall Process

Each pilot-intervention went through the following process:

First, the use case is described and **key quantitative data points** are highlighted – such as total volumes of materials – and retrieved as key variables for the development of the different mass or energy flow models that will be used for the environmental impact assessment of the intervention. The five-year goal of the specific intervention is also retrieved and, in the majority of cases, used to project longer-term impact once the intervention has scaled.

Second, the **baseline** is modelled, based both on the use case description and the data already compiled and analysed in REFLOW Deliverable D.3.2 within the MFAs. The baseline quantifies the business-as-usual (BAU) material or energy flows that would be occurring if the REFLOW interventions were not in place.

Third, the **REFLOW intervention's** (short term scenario) material or energy flows are modelled for the duration of the intervention test period, which varies per pilot and per intervention (from four weeks for the Milan pilot's BOTTO intervention to one year for the Amsterdam pilot's Swapshops). **The longer-term scenario** (five-year post-REFLOW) represents the **intervention once scaled to reach its five-year goal** set by each pilot.

Fourth, a life-cycle approach is adopted to compare the short-term and longer-term scenarios' environmental impacts relative to the baseline's own impacts. Environmental data are retrieved from life-cycle databases, such as Ecoinvent 3.8,² from literature published from authoritative sources, such as the JRC,³ or directly by interviewing domain experts. For pilots which had a focus on a material flow (Amsterdam, Vejle, Milan, and Paris) rather than an energy flow (Cluj-Napoca and Berlin), two life-cycle stages were specifically selected for this analysis, namely the **production and end-of-life stages**. For the production stage, since these pilots have established interventions that help capture materials at high value and insert them back into their respective systems, the result is to reduce **the production of new virgin/raw materials** to meet the current demand. As a result, the impacts are quantified in terms of 'avoided' impacts since the production processes were avoided thanks to the intervention. For the **end-of-life stage**, the impacts of this stage are compared directly with the baseline, whether the intervention removes the end-of-life stage altogether (e.g. in Milan, food recovered is consumed) or changes it for a more circular treatment process (e.g. in Amsterdam, moving from incineration to recycling). When looking at non-material flows, only the production stage was taken into consideration in the calculation.

² <https://ecoinvent.org/the-ecoinvent-database/>

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/joint-research-centre_en

2. AMSTERDAM PILOT

Introduction

The REFLOW Amsterdam pilot focused on the way textiles are discarded and reused, and how they can be returned to the local textile system. The current challenge is that home textiles are often wrongly discarded for two reasons: a lack of awareness and sub-optimal ways of collecting textiles. More than 70% of home textiles will eventually be incinerated rather than reused in Amsterdam. Simultaneously, the demand for recycled and recyclable material is growing slowly, due to an absence of commercial uptake. The Amsterdam pilot has outlined two interconnected scenarios that tackle these challenges: 1) a short-term scenario focusing on necessary behavioural change among its citizens, and 2) a long-term scenario focusing on industrial impact, aiming to increase the provision of feedstock for the recycling industry, and, in turn, to increase the supply of products made of recycled resources, in order to decrease the percentage of virgin textile fibres used. Within each of these two scenarios, the Amsterdam pilot included the design of two specific interventions on consumer textiles via the Swapshop implementation and healthcare textiles via the design of reusable isolation gowns. The Amsterdam pilot includes the Municipality of Amsterdam,⁴ Pakhuis de Zwijger,⁵ Waag⁶ and BMA⁷ Techne. A more extensive description of the pilot and its activities can be found in REFLOW Deliverable D1.5.

⁴ <https://www.amsterdam.nl/en/>

⁵ <https://www.dezwijger.nl>

⁶ <https://waag.org>

⁷ <https://amsterdameconomicboard.com/samenwerkingspartner/bma-techne/>

Figure 3. Amsterdam's first Swapshop location on Haarlemmerdijk street.

Intervention 1: The Swapshop

Summary of the intervention

The Swapshop is a second-hand clothing store where customers can bring their clothes and swap them with other clothes. The use case focuses on creating a physical location to collect and sell second-hand consumer clothes to increase high-value textile reuse locally, and avoid the incineration of wearable garments, or the export of collected textiles in foreign countries. In 2019, almost 9,000 tonnes per year of household textiles were incinerated within Amsterdam. Almost a third of these incinerated textiles could have been worn again directly and absorbed into the second-hand market. This is the focus of the first use case. In contrast, the close to 3,000 tonnes of textiles properly discarded into the textile waste stream in 2019, are mostly shipped outside of the Netherlands, and therefore do not remain within Amsterdam's textile system (REFLOW Deliverable D.3.2). The Swapshop was developed as an idea to resolve these challenges.

Thanks to REFLOW OS, the Swapshop can keep track of the items that are sold to customers, even when the items leave the shop and possibly return later on (see Figure 4). Using the data storage capabilities of REFLOW OS, the Swapshop could also associate information to each textile item that is being swapped. The information can, in essence, create a 'story' of the piece of garment in the hope that this new insight into the

Figure 4. Life-cycle stages of The Swapshop.

life-cycle of the product changes the perception of the next users and creates a personal connection with the garment, therefore nudging them to prolong its lifetime. Garments that cannot be exchanged as they are too worn out, are manually sorted by staff and disposed of appropriately. For example, items made from textiles with a high percentage of cotton are directed to the Denim Deal,⁸ and other items might go to organisations such as Dress for Success,⁹ or external enterprises like I-DID,¹⁰ which produces new items out of the collected textiles for sale on the B2B market. Within the last few months of REFLOW and the next following months, the pilot aims to open **six Swapshops**, each starting with a capacity of **four tonnes/year** in their first year.

⁸ <https://www.houseofdenim.org/denim-deal>

⁹ <https://dressforsuccess.org>

¹⁰ <https://www.i-did.nl>

The five-year goal

The Amsterdam pilot has set itself a five-year goal to divert around 200 tonnes of clothes from incineration through Swapshops. Thus, increasing the flow of rewearable textiles and garments through second-hand shops and keeping a high proportion of clothing in circulation within Amsterdam. To achieve this ambitious goal, the pilot aims to open approximately 20 **Swapshops through** a franchise business case, each with an increased capacity of about 10 tonnes/year for a total of **200 tonnes per year**. This total amount is used to calculate the potential scaled impacts of the solution.

Methodology

To be able to assess the environmental impact reduction of the intervention, the Swapshop intervention was compared to what would have happened to the collected clothes should the shops not have been present. The baseline analysis calculations were performed based on the current capacity of the Swapshops opened within the last year of REFLOW and in the months shortly following the end of the project, which amounts to 24 tonnes of textile items saved in a year. The impacts (see Figure 4) are calculated assuming that the garments are used by two users, hence they are purchased once new and once at the Swapshop.

Production stage

Baseline & Intervention. The Swapshop intervention helps avoid the production of new virgin textile products through promoting the reuse of clothes. The 'avoided' production impacts of the 24 tonnes of textiles are therefore assessed through, 1) quantifying the weighted average impact per kg of fibre for CO₂-eq emitted, water, and land use during the production stage (see Equation 1), and 2) multiplying the weighted average by the total amounts of textile saved, 24 tonnes (see Equation 2). The average fibre mix (i.e. fibre composition of clothes) in Amsterdam is retrieved from the REFLOW D3.2 textile material flow analysis.

Equation 1.

$$\text{Weighted average impact per kg of textile} = \frac{\sum (\text{fibre weight}_n * \text{fibre impact}_n)}{\sum (\text{fibre weight}_n)}$$

Table 1. CO₂-eq., water and land use impacts for different fibres (Main Source: Beton et al. 2014,¹¹ Ecoinvent 3.8, & see references for water and land use impacts source).

Fibre type	Fibre weight	Production GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂ -eq/tonne)	Water use (m ³ /tonne) - production only*	Land use (ha/tonne) - production only*
Cotton	35.6%	22.5	1,986	1.05
Wool	8.2%	19.5	135	31.00
Silk	0.3%	15.0	900	6.87
Flax	3.3%	26.0	143	0.97
Viscose	8.8%	23.0	413	0.70
Polyester	26.8%	27.2	36	0.0
Acrylic	3.7%	37.7	210	0.0
Nylon/Polyamid	7.7%	30.9	185	0.0
PU/PP/EA	4.4%	25.5	43	0.0

* Production accounts for all the steps before fibre production.

Equation 2.

$$\text{Total avoided impact} = \text{Weighted average impact} * \text{Mass textile saved}$$

End-of-Life Stage

Baseline. Thanks to the intervention, 24 tonnes of textile will be re-used and therefore avoid the traditional waste treatment channels of the city. In Amsterdam, clothes are likely incinerated (~75%) or sent abroad for recycling or low-value reuse as it represents their average end-of-life fate (REFLOW Deliverable D3.2). To simplify the comparison, only the total amount of textile treated in the Netherlands, therefore the quantity that would have been incinerated (75% of the 24 tonnes) was considered since sparse information is available for the remaining textile (~25%) that would have been collected separately and exported abroad. Assuming that the Swapshop user would bring the clothing item purchased back to the Swapshop after its useful life, the item would avoid incineration as it will be recycled through the diversion from the Swapshop. When assessing the end-of-life impacts of the baseline, it is assumed that the garments are produced from raw material twice and incinerated twice (for two users). The GHG impacts of textile incineration are compiled in Table 2.

¹¹ The W (Beton et al., 2014) was used in REFLOW D3.2. and additional data retrieved from the Ecoinvent 3.8 LCA database (on a mass per unit basis).

Equation 3.

$$\text{Total impacts incineration} = \text{total textile} * \text{incineration share} * \text{incineration impacts} * 2$$

Table 2. CO₂-eq impacts textile incineration (Source:Ecoinvent 3.8).

Fibre type	Incineration GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂ -eq/tonne)
Mixed textile	0.75

Results

Intervention. Recovery of 24 tonnes through Swapshops could avoid the emissions of about 593 tonnes of CO₂-eq during the production of virgin textile products. Additionally, about 19,000 m³ of water would be saved, as well as almost 48 ha of land that would have been used to grow the different fibres.

Concerning the end-of-life impacts, should the majority of the 24 tonnes of textile (75%) be incinerated in the baseline scenario, this would cause the emissions of almost 27 tonnes of CO₂-eq. On the other hand, implementing six Swapshops will emit about 81 tonnes of CO₂ in the year through energy use and close to five tonnes of CO₂ with the mechanical recycling process.

Overall, the intervention allows the savings of nearly 534 tonnes CO₂-eq, 19,000 m³ of water, and 48 ha of land.

Five-year scenario. Within the next five years, the Amsterdam pilot has set a target to recover 200 tonnes of textile items through the deployment of 20 Swapshops. Following the same methodology used to assess the intervention impacts, the deployment of this solution to this scale would prevent emissions from an estimated 4,939 tonnes of CO₂-eq during the textile production processes, as well as the use of almost 160,000 m³ of water and almost 400 ha of land to grow and produce the fibres.

Equation 4.

$$\text{Total store impacts} = \text{Total electricity consumed} * \text{kg CO}_2\text{eq} / \text{kWh} + \text{total gas consumed} * \text{kgCO}_2\text{eq} / \text{m}^3 \text{ gas} + \text{mechanical recycling impacts}$$

Concerning the end-of-life impacts, should the majority of the 200 tonnes of textile (75%) be recycled after two use phases instead of being incinerated, a total of about 186 tonnes of CO₂ would be avoided when comparing incineration to recycling. The energy required for the 20 Swapshops would lead to about 269 tonnes of CO₂-eq. Overall, the scaling of the intervention would result in a net saving of about 4,990 tonnes of CO₂-eq.

Thus, the vast majority of environmental benefits lie in the avoided production impacts upstream in the supply chain, while locally, the re-use solution may lead to a small increase in local CO₂-eq emissions (mainly from the energy). However, by increasing the capacity of each Swapshop, a reduction of impact per tonne of textile can be observed. Overall, considering both the production, the use, and end-of-life stages, the recovery of 200 tonnes of textile clothes still leads to a net saving of 4,856 tonnes of CO₂-eq, as well as a large savings of water and land use. Lastly, it can be noted that the Swapshops are also encouraging customers to return the second-hand clothes back to their stores once they do not need them anymore. Therefore, the clothes may have additional use-cycles beyond their first second-hand cycle, each cycle contributing further in avoiding the production of new virgin textile products.

The benefits of the intervention, both in the short- and long-term are highlighted below (see Table 3, Figure 5, and Figure 6).

Figure 5. Raw material use comparison for the Swapshops intervention.

Figure 6. GHG emissions comparison for the Swapshops intervention.

Table 3. Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline, the intervention, and the scaled intervention for the Swapshop intervention.

Environmental impacts	Baseline	Baseline for scaled intervention	Intervention	Scaled Intervention
Textile production (tonnes) ¹²	48	400	24	200
Textile production avoided (tonnes)	0	0	24	200
Textile incinerated/landfilled (tonnes)	48	400	0	0
Textile reuse/recycled (tonnes)	0	0	24	200
Total CO ₂ -eq emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	534	4,856
Total water use avoided (m ³)	0	0	19,000	160,000
Total land use avoided (ha)	0	0	48	400

Assumptions and limitations

The environmental impacts are calculated assuming the garments exchanged through the Swapshops are purchased by only one user and then brought back to the Swapshop (two uses), where it will be properly disposed through mechanical recycling. This scenario was selected for simplicity and to compare minimal uses. However, in reality, the garments can go through this cycle multiple times and may have much more than two users depending on the time each user keeps the clothing items. Each supplemental use drastically reduces the environmental impacts of the intervention as the production impacts are avoided for any additional use.

For the simplicity of the LCA calculation, it was assumed that one kilogram of textile raw materials and fibres yield exactly a kilogram of finished textile. In reality, more raw materials are needed for the production of a kilogram of finished textile, which would bring the environmental impacts of the production even higher.

¹² For the baseline scenarios, the actual quantity of clothing saved is multiplied by two – given the fact that the garments would be produced twice should the Swapshops not be present.

Discussion on scaling and barriers to market entry and resource monitoring

The Amsterdam pilot has set itself on operating a cultural change in terms of how its residents manage their textile clothes and garments. At the onset of REFLOW (REFLOW D3.2), it was established that the vast majority of textile products were not properly separated by Amsterdam's residents, and even readily reusable clothes ended up in the incineration plant. The intervention developed by the pilot once scaled across the city can have a significant impact in providing visible points of collection throughout the city and normalise the use of secondary markets for the purchase of clothes and garments. Beyond the physical capacity of the shops to collect clothes – which will not be enough to manage by themselves the large volumes of textile released by Amsterdam's households – it is their ability to spur behavioural change with a bottom-up approach at a neighbourhood-level that can enact a larger change in the metabolism of textile waste in the city. As previously mentioned, increasing the number of cycles (users) a garment can have can drastically influence the avoided impacts. With its five-year goal, the pilot will be able to provide textile clothes outlets across residential and commercial neighbourhoods and save hundreds of tonnes of textiles from incineration, and reduce the purchase of new clothes by Amsterdam residents. This will contribute to reducing the textile flow throughput in Amsterdam's urban metabolism. It will also positively affect the local ecosystem of textile by contributing to the growth of the local market for second hand textile products, and increase the connection across the local value chain – from residents to second-hand shops, and collection, sorting, and recycling.

There are however several barriers to market entry that this intervention will face over the coming years. First, the lack of physical spaces available to host the 10 Swapshops across the city to receive, sort, repair and re-distribute the textile items is a key limiting factor. The availability and high-costs of commercial spaces could constitute one of the main challenges for the expansion of this intervention. Additionally, at a practical level, there is also a gap in skills in order to have enough staff capable of assessing the quality of textiles during the sorting process in Swapshops. As a result, a lack of trained workforce may hinder the scaling of the intervention. Finally, Swapshops may face competition from independent commercial clothing retailers that also seek to develop a second-hand market, for example those connected to I:Collect¹³ (H&M, C&A). This competition backed by large private investment could challenge Swapshops expansion in Amsterdam as they have larger commercial spaces and benefits from already established positions in the textile market.

For the Swapshop intervention, the monitoring of resource flows represents a key challenge but also an opportunity to set it apart from its competitors. In the case of this intervention, the development of REFLOW OS can provide the foundation of circular monitoring, helping track the textile items through their different use cycles. A key challenge that will need to be addressed will be the buy-in of Swapshop customers in the tracking system and how to collect their 'textile story' for each item in a practical but still meaningful way. The monitoring of the resource flows will support the understanding of the use-cycle of textiles items, their use patterns, and their overall positive impacts as they go through various use cycles.

¹³ <https://www.ico-spirit.com/en/>

Figure 7. The Circular Isolation Gown developed by the Amsterdam pilot.

Intervention 2: Isolation gowns

Summary of the intervention

This use case focuses on medical isolation gowns used by nurses during patient treatment to protect them from contamination. In the majority of cases, these gowns are discarded after every single use to avoid cross contamination and as a cost-cutting measure. Within Amsterdam alone, millions of these disposable gowns are therefore being used on a single-use basis, then thrown away and subsequently incinerated. The Circular Isolation Gowns solution incorporates circular product design to tackle this issue and develop reusable isolation gowns for the healthcare sector. The solution is in collaboration with CleanLease,¹⁴ the leasing company which provides textile products for the healthcare and hospitality industry and that will be responsible to deliver the gowns to the hospitals and collect them for washing and quality control.

The Circular Isolation Gowns are designed to compete both on functionality and comfort with the disposable ones that currently dominate the market and can be washed up to 100 times (Figure 8). CleanLease uses its own proprietary system to track the gowns through every different step of the process, and inspect them for quality, wash them, and then ship them again if not discarded. This material passport gives CleanLease insights into the material flow of the Circular Isolation Gowns. This solution creates value through the information derived from track and trace and the transparency

which this provides to the user. The prototype of the Circular Isolation Gowns has been finalised and the next step is for the gowns to undergo in-use trials to gather feedback on the ease of use, comfort, care, maintenance, the implication for use, and laundry logistics.

The gowns are being locally produced by Makers Unite,¹⁵ who will manufacture the first **3,000 gowns replacing a total of 300,000 disposable gowns**. At the end of REFLOW, the project will continue and move to the next stage within a new funded project named LOCAAS (Local As A Service) for which funding and planning have been allocated for the coming two years. In this second stage, around 25,000 isolation gowns will be produced and leased to Coordaan,¹⁶ a care provider, OLVG,¹⁷ the city hospital for Greater Amsterdam, and other local hospitals.

¹⁴ <https://nl.cleanlease.com/nl/home>

¹⁵ <https://makersunite.eu>

¹⁶ <https://www.cordaan.nl>

¹⁷ <https://www.olvg.nl>

The five-year goal

The Amsterdam pilot has set itself a five-year goal to replace **5,000,000 disposable** isolation gowns by **50,000 reusable** ones (REFLOW Deliverable D5.3). Connected to this goal, the pilot aims to overcome the reticence of public healthcare workers and decision-makers to change the current use of disposable gowns. Thus, an emphasis on comfort and price-competitiveness was placed early in the circular design process.

Figure 8. Life-cycle stages of the Isolation Gowns use case.

Methodology

Baseline. To be able to calculate environmental impact reduction of the intervention, a baseline scenario before the beginning of REFLOW was used. For the circular isolation gowns intervention, it was assumed that all isolation gowns were originally made from polypropylene (PP). The baseline analysis calculations were performed assuming that 300,000 single-use gowns were used in a year at an Amsterdam hospital, each weighing 65 grams. To better compare the impacts of the baseline scenario with those of the REFLOW intervention, the total GHG impacts were calculated by use (300,000 uses). The water use and land use impacts were calculated solely for the raw material production phase, for which the nature of the materials used between the baseline and the intervention present a significant difference in terms of impacts. The total quantity of the gowns used and their individual weight were multiplied by the per unit impacts which provided a total yearly environmental impact for each scenario (see Equation 1).

Equation 1.

Total impact = Quantity of gowns * Gown unit material mass * impact

Table 4. Life-cycle impacts of polypropylene isolation gowns (Source: Ecoinvent 3.8, Anton Luiken (Alcon Advies BV) & Ger Brinks (BMA~Technie)).

Life-cycle stage	GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂ -eq/tonne)	Water use (m ³ /tonne) - production only	Land use (ha/tonne) - production only
PP granules production	1.97	43	0
Spunbond non-woven fabric production (from granules to finished textile)	2.41	-	-
Incineration (with power generation)	0.75	-	-

Intervention. The Amsterdam pilot plans to replace a total of 300,000 single-use plastic gowns by 3,000 reusable cotton gowns. The replacement implies that each reusable gown will be used a total of 100 times each to provide the same amount of uses (Figure 8). The cotton used by the pilot was described to have virgin origins. As part of the pilot’s intervention, it was required that the cotton gowns are mechanically recycled after their useful life (100 uses), rather than incinerated as is customary. Given the unavailability of the cotton mechanical recycling impacts on the LCA database, a proxy had to be used. According to Anton Luiken, a textile expert and participant in the Amsterdam pilot, the mechanical recycling impacts are mostly originating from the energy input of the process. Hence, the energy used on the Dutch grid for a kilogram of cotton was employed (see Appendix).

Between each use, the soiled gowns are collected and washed by CleanLease. From the total environmental impacts calculated of the use of 3,000 reusable cotton gowns, again, an impact was calculated per use for a clearer comparison.

Table 5. Life-cycle impacts of cotton isolation gowns (Source: Ecoinvent 3.8, Anton Luiken (Alcon Advies BV) & Ger Brinks (BMA-Techne)).

Life-cycle stage	GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂ -eq/tonne)	Water use (m ³ /tonne) - production only	Land use (ha/tonne) - production only
Cotton production	1.13	1,986	0.95
Fibre production	3.52	-	-
Yarn spinning	4.39	-	-
Weaving	6.07	-	-
Pre-treating, painting, finishing	3.04	-	-
Washing (100x)	21.33	-	-
Mechanical recycling	0.26	-	-

Results

Baseline. The analysis of the baseline yielded that the annual use of 300,000 PP gowns was responsible for emitting about 100 tonnes of CO₂-eq (from cradle to grave), representing about 0.33 kg of CO₂-eq for each gown used. The production of the PP granules yielded a total of 839 m³ of water use, while not requiring any agricultural land. Overall, the total amount of plastic required and sent to incineration represented 19.5 tonnes.

Intervention. The Amsterdam pilot aims to use 3,000 reusable and recyclable cotton gowns. Over their entire life-cycle (cradle to cradle), each cotton gown will emit about 10 kg of CO₂-eq or 8 kg of CO₂ for recycled cotton gowns). Since these gowns are to be washed and reused about 100 times and recycled at the end of their life-cycle, their emission per use will be 0.10 kg per use, which is ~80% less per use, than a single-use PP gowns. The use of 3,000 cotton gowns will lead to the emissions of nearly 30 tonnes of CO₂-eq (or 24 tonnes for recycled cotton gowns), representing therefore a total reduction of 70 tonnes compared to the 300,000 PP single-use gowns. While the life-cycle process of cotton gowns present a net savings of CO₂-eq emissions when compared to the one of PP granules, the cotton production is more resource intensive than its synthetic alternative. The production of raw materials would require a total of 1,490 m³ of water and about 0.79 ha of agricultural land, which is 651 m³ of water more than for PP and almost one ha of more land. In this project, the water and land resources required for cotton recycling were not measured. However, it is expected that the resource intensity is much lower in terms of land use, while a more thorough analysis should be done regarding water use. From a raw material perspective, this intervention will require the use of 0.75 tonnes of cotton, the mechanical recycling performed on the reusable gowns will prevent the textile resource to go to incineration.

Five-year scenario. Within the next five years, the Amsterdam pilot has set a target to produce 50,000 cotton reusable gowns to replace 5,000,000 disposable gowns. Following the same methodology used to assess the baseline and intervention impacts, the deployment of this solution to this scale would lead to a reduction of 1,171 tonnes of CO₂-eq as the PP gowns would be responsible for 1,668 tonnes of CO₂ while the reusable cotton gowns will emit 497 tonnes CO₂-eq. On the other hand, the raw materials production would require 10,850 m³ of water and about 13 ha of land more than for the PP granules production. The total amount of cotton required would be approximately 12.5 tonnes, which will then be mechanically recycled and either fed back into the local isolation production system or for other textile use. The avoided use of 5,000,000 PP gowns will help avoid 325 tonnes of virgin plastic material, and their subsequent incineration in Amsterdam.

The benefits of the intervention, both in the short- and long-term, are highlighted below (see Table 6, Figure 9, and Figure 10).

Table 6. Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline, the intervention, and the scaled intervention for the Isolation Gowns intervention.

Environmental impacts	Baseline	Baseline for scaled intervention	Intervention	Scaled intervention
Raw material use (tonnes)	19.5	325	0.75	12.5
Textile incinerated/landfilled (tonnes)	19.5	325	0	0
Textile reused/recycled (tonnes)	0	0	0.75	12.5
Total CO ₂ -eq emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	70	1,171
CO ₂ -eq emissions avoided per use (kg/use)	0	0	0.23	0.23
Total water use (m ³)	839	13,975	1,489	24,825
Total land use (ha)	0	0	0.79	13

Figure 9. Raw material use comparison for the Isolation Gowns intervention.

Figure 10. GHG emissions comparison for the Isolation Gowns intervention.

Assumptions & Limitations

The gown manufacture for both the PP and the cotton gowns were omitted; there is no available data on the LCA dataset and it can be assumed that relative impacts are quite similar.¹⁸ Transportation also has been omitted for both processes.

Discussion: Scaling and barriers to market entry and resource monitoring

The City of Amsterdam is home to 13 hospitals, resulting in millions of single-use, plastic-based, disposable gowns being thrown away and incinerated in the city, every year. The intervention developed by the Amsterdam pilot once scaled to all hospitals in the city can positively affect the local healthcare sector metabolism, and thus the city's overall metabolism by reducing the throughput of virgin material and waste. With its ambitious five-year goal, the pilot will be able, over the coming years, to further refine the circular alternative of reusable gowns, and demonstrate the viability of this intervention to the local healthcare sector. As it is scaled, tens of thousands of tonnes of virgin materials could be saved, carbon emissions avoided, and local air pollution reduced through avoided incineration. Conversely, the resource intensity of the virgin cotton production process should be noted; it thus becomes even more important to shift the raw material of the reusable gowns towards recycled cotton. Increasing the use of reusable gowns throughout the city, and even the Netherlands, would increase the availability of raw materials for a cotton gown recycling process to produce new recycled gowns, thus closing the textile loop. This intervention will also affect the local ecosystem of the city that play a role in managing its urban metabolism - it will contribute to the growth of a new local market for both recycled materials and for recycling companies, and increase connection across the local value chain, from manufacturing, to leasing/maintenance, and collection, sorting, and recycling.

Nonetheless, there are several barriers to market entry that this intervention will face over the coming years. First, the healthcare sector is heavily regulated to respect high hygiene standards. As a result, these regulations have a direct impact on the type of materials and their life-cycle, which currently favour single-use and incineration as a waste treatment method. The gown will therefore need to fit into the current regulatory landscape and provide guarantee of safety for hospital personnel. Additionally, price competitiveness will be one of the major barriers: the largest shareholders of the isolation markets are able to source plastic material at very low prices, while the circular intervention depends on (currently) higher-cost materials. Finally, to fully close the local material loops, and achieve the scaling envisioned by the pilot, local manufacturing capabilities – regarding both skills and infrastructure – will need to be increasingly developed, especially for key points in the supply chain such as spinning, weaving, and final manufacturing.

¹⁸ http://www.sustainabilityroadmap.org/pims/pdfs/pim247_lifecycle_assessment_disposable_versus_reusable.pdf

For both Amsterdam interventions, the monitoring of resource flows represents a challenge and a barrier to be solved, also to coordinate the recalibration of the local urban metabolism. In the case of this intervention, the development of REFLOW OS can provide the foundation of circular monitoring, helping connect the different actors in the local supply chain. A key challenge that will need to be addressed will be the incremental onboarding of currently missing actors in the value chains onto this platform, and the integration of REFLOW OS into already existing systems, such as the one used by CleanLease to track their leased products. The monitoring of the resource flows will go hand-in-hand with the comprehension of impacts and how they evolved through time as the intervention scales.

Material development research outputs

Alternative bio-based textiles

Developed in T3.2, material development research has focused on biobased textiles for Amsterdam. Since the pilot was focused on enhancing the circularity of local textiles, early on showed interest in the discussion of alternative fibres, and thus to the implications of bio-based textiles as a circular and regenerative alternative. To explore this possibility further, a roundtable was implemented with the above-mentioned pilot members and invited stakeholders from universities, research centres, and garment brands. The aim of this meeting was to determine key issues regarding the circular production of bio-based textiles. As a main output, the discussion resulted in the [structure of a bio-textiles chapter](#) that could complement the work developed by the pilot in the [Circular Textiles Booklet](#). The output of this work could also be integrated in the further development of the isolation gowns.

3. BERLIN PILOT

Introduction

The REFLOW Berlin pilot focuses on wastewater heat recovery as a means to guide the city towards climate-neutral heating. Wastewater heat is generated as a by-product of water use in industrial processes, and in the everyday domestic life of citizens. Wastewater often retains large amounts of thermal energy, but much of this heat potential is lost to the sewer system. Within European policy circles,¹⁹ wastewater heat utilisation is considered a valid option for circular heating systems. Throughout Europe, due to the geopolitical challenges happening between Russia and Ukraine, renewable energy and waste heat have become priorities for local and central policymakers. This is particularly true for Germany, which highly depends on the import of Russian gas. By mapping the flows on a visual interface and providing clear insights on the wastewater heat potential, the pilot aims to develop a marketable solution that can drive the development of wastewater heat recovery, across Berlin and other municipalities.

The Berlin consortium includes four key actors. The first partner, Berliner Wasserbetriebe²⁰ (BWB) is the sole operator of the sewer network and has the role to propose new offers as an energy supplier. The second, Prototypes for Europe,²¹ act as technology transfer experts responsible for coordination, control, and future of the project. The third one, Fraunhofer Fokus,²² has the role of securing software systems for the public sector, and finally, MCS DATALABS²³ is a software and hardware IT firm that focuses on backend development of this project.

¹⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/422033-waste-heat-valorisation>

²⁰ <https://www.bwb.de/de/index.php>

²¹ <https://www.prototypes.berlin/>

²² <https://www.fokus.fraunhofer.de/en>

²³ <https://mcs-datalabs.com/>

Figure 11. The Waste Water Heat Radar map.

Intervention: Wastewater Heat Radar

Summary of the intervention

The Wastewater Heat Radar (WWHR) aims at solving the match-making challenges between supply and demand of wastewater heat by providing a user-friendly digital platform. While mapping the potential emitters of wastewater heat from local infrastructures, the potential of heat extracted from heat pumps can be measured and trigger the interest of local consumers. Within Berlin alone, the amount of wastewater heat amounts to hundreds of megawatts of usable energy.

Within the REFLOW timeline, the Berlin pilot has mapped the Berlin metropolitan region wastewater heat potential through an open-source web application in the style of a radar (see Figure 11). This application is targeted to urban planners, engineers, architects, and property developers to use the potential wastewater heat as an energy source in new construction and retrofitting projects. On the database, the potentially recoverable wastewater heat (extraction power and heating load) can be assessed for different addresses and sites can be compared with one another. To create traction for new implementations, the Wastewater Heat Radar showcases various reference projects in nearby districts of the city where waste heat technologies have been implemented successfully.

Figure 12. Open Data Dashboard.

The solution bridges the gap between supply and demand by way of matchmaking and addresses the lack of overview of supply and demand at municipality level, thus increasing both the awareness of the potential of wastewater heat, but also contributing to its recovery. Ultimately, this dashboard can provide key information about locations of buildings in which heat recovery can take place to reduce their energy costs, and improve their sustainability profile. From a strategic point of view, the Berlin pilot has been working on the development of a solution to expand the use of the dashboard beyond the pilot phase, and beyond Berlin’s sole boundaries (REFLOW Deliverable 1.5).

The five-year goal

The Berlin pilot has set itself a five-year goal to provide a fully functional digital and organisational platform for optimising the use of waste-heat via the medium of water as a means of reducing the CO₂-footprint of properties in metropolitan areas.

Methodology

The environmental assessment of Berlin pilot intervention has been developed differently than the other pilots in this deliverable. The pilot did not have a direct environmental impact through the development of the Wastewater Heat Radar dashboard, which made their short-term and long-term environmental impact assessment more difficult. Nonetheless, the “potential” environmental impacts of extracting waste heat from the sewer system can be quantified to show the potential benefits of a scaled, “on-the-ground” intervention at the city-scale that would be supported by the web application. This assessment was carried out by the Berlin pilot team itself as it was developed in parallel with the construction of the Wastewater Heat Radar web application. Within this particular context, the overall methodology employed by the pilot team is described below.

Input values. The pilot team assessed the potential of the intervention using the following input values. First, the total annual theoretical waste heat available in the sewer system was quantified based on BWB’s preliminary assessment performed in 2020 and set to 275,000 kW.²⁴ Assumptions for the extractable heat potential, the share of waste heat that can actually be recovered by heat pumps were based on a literature review and expert interviews and set to 33% of the theoretical available wastewater heat. The wastewater heat is recovered through heat pumps that themselves use electricity to function, thus the energy performance (coefficient of performance, COP) of pumps was accounted for based on BWB’s evaluation²⁵ from 2021 of four heat pumps installed in 2020. The COP was determined to be 3.35 (unitless). Additionally, the heat pumps’ yearly full-load hours (when the pumps work at full-capacity) were assumed based on expert knowledge and set at 1,800 h/year. Finally, the carbon intensity of energy produced from natural gas in Germany (the main energy used for heating purposes the city) and the carbon intensity of the German electricity mix (used to run heat pumps) were set at 299 g CO₂-eq/kWh²⁶ and 366 g CO₂-eq/kWh²⁷ in 2020, respectively. The pilot also assessed how the intervention would fare based on a carbon intensity electricity grid projected for 2030 that has slightly decarbonised to 250 g CO₂-eq/kWh.

²⁴ Gütler. (2020). BWB internal study.

²⁵ Hansem. (2021). BWB internal study

²⁶ <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/165421/umfrage/co2-ausstoss-nach-heizsystem-in-deutschland/>

²⁷ <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/38897/umfrage/co2-emissionsfaktor-fuer-den-strommix-in-deutschland-seit-1990/#professional>

Calculating CO₂-eq emissions from heat pumps deployed at City

The total extractable heat, also known as the wastewater heat capacity, is calculated based on the total theoretical available wastewater heat and what share of this total can be actually extracted by heat pumps (see Equation 1).

The total extractable heat, also known as the **wastewater heat capacity**, is calculated based on the total **theoretical available wastewater heat** and what share of this total can be actually extracted by heat pumps (see Equation 1).

Equation 1.

$$\text{Wastewater heat capacity} = \text{Theoretical available wastewater heat} * \text{Extraction potential}$$

The **coefficient of performance** or COP of a heat pump is the ratio of useful heating or cooling provided to work required (see Equation 2).

Equation 2.

$$\text{COP} = \text{Heat capacity of heatpumps} / \text{Electric capacity}$$

Source: https://amsterdamgreencampus.nl/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Hillenius_TEO_Final.pdf

Figure 13. Conceptual model of the heat capacity of heat pumps.

The net **heat capacity of heat pumps** is calculated in function of the wastewater heat capacity and the electric capacity of the heat pump. As the electric capacity is originally unknown, the heat capacity of heat pumps can be given in terms of the COP and the wastewater heat capacity (see Figure 13, Equation 3, and Equation 4).²⁸

Equation 3.

$$\text{Heat capacity of heatpumps} = \text{Wastewater heat capacity} + \text{Electric capacity}$$

Equation 4.

$$\text{Heat capacity of heatpumps} = \text{Wastewater heat capacity} * \frac{\text{COP}}{\text{COP}-1}$$

The **total heat energy produced** through the heat pump is a function of the **heat capacity of the heat pumps** and their **total number of full-load hours in a year** (Equation 5).

Equation 5.

$$\text{Total heat energy produced} = \text{Heat capacity of heat pumps} * \text{Total full load hours/year}$$

From the **electric capacity** calculated with Equation 3, the **total electricity used** by the heat pumps to extract the total amount of heat can be calculated (Equation 6).

Equation 6.

$$\text{Total electricity used} = \text{Electric capacity} * \text{Total full load hours/year}$$

The **total CO₂-eq emissions** in tonnes to produce heat energy with the heat pumps are then calculated based on the **carbon intensity** of the German electricity grid in 2020 and based on carbon intensity projections for 2030 (Equation 7).

Equation 7.

$$\text{CO}_{2\text{eq}} \text{ heat production}_{\text{heat pumps}} = \text{Total electricity used} * \text{Carbon intensity}_{\text{electricity}} / 10^6$$

Calculating CO₂-eq emissions for the baseline scenario

The Berlin pilot compared the **total amount of heat energy extracted** from the sewer to the equivalent amount of heat energy provided when using natural gas as an energy source, which constitutes the baseline (Equation 8).

²⁸ <https://research.tue.nl/en/studentTheses/optimal-design-and-operation-of-a-solar-thermal-collector-field-i>

Equation 8.

$$CO_{2eq}^{electricity\ used\ heat\ pumps} = Total\ heat\ energy\ used * Carbon\ intensity_{nat.gas} / 10^6$$

Results

The total amount of extractable heat from Berlin’s sewer system was estimated to be 90,750 kW, based on the theoretical potential of 275,000 kW of available heat and the extractable heat potential of 33%, which presents a very conservative estimate.

The net capacity that could be extracted via heat pumps was quantified at 129,367 kW, which considering a total 1,800 hours of full loads for installed heat pumps within a year, may amount up to 232.86 GWh of heat being produced for direct use within Berlin’s buildings.

The total electricity used to extract this quantity of heat would in this case amount to 69,510,638 kWh. Based on the 2020 German’s electricity mix, this would cause almost 25,441 tonnes of CO₂-eq to be emitted. Considering future decarbonization efforts in Germany by 2030, this amount of electricity would cause the emissions of 17,378 tonnes of CO₂-eq. In comparison, providing 233 GWh of heat to the city via the baseline energy source of natural gas would emit 69,625 tonnes of CO₂-eq.

Thus, a fully-scaled waste heat recovery system at the city-scaled could save 44,184 tonnes of CO₂ based on an electric grid in the decade following 2020 (Figure 14) and 52,248 tonnes of CO₂ considering the projected 2030’s electricity grid.

Figure 14. GHG emissions comparison for wastewater heat.

Discussion on scaling and barriers to market entry and resource monitoring

The Berlin pilot has set its course on supporting the recovery of waste heat as a circular flow to drive the decarbonisation of Berlin's energy system. Waste heat recovery has been emerging in recent years as a promising solution for sustainable urban heat district systems. Nonetheless, it suffers from an overall lack of awareness about this specific energy source and a lack of quantified assessment to map the waste heat flows available in urban spaces and assess the technical feasibility of heat recovery. The Wastewater Heat Radar is a first step to overcome these challenges. By providing granular information on the waste heat potential throughout the city, it will facilitate the emergence of future projects in Berlin by showcasing promising use cases. As shown by the total amount of heat that can be recovered and used within the city, and the tens of thousands of tonnes of CO₂-eq emission reduction that can be achieved by substituting natural gas-based heating by waste heat-powered heat pumps, the waste heat from the sewer if recovered **at city-scale** can positively affect the energy metabolism of Berlin. By launching several pilots over the coming years and increasing the number of wastewater heat recovery implementations, in partnership with BWB, the Berlin pilot can strengthen the local urban system by connecting technologists, urban planners, real estate developers, and citizens to enact change in their energy systems. Once those have proven successful, the long-term development is geared towards the implementation of waste heat recovery systems, throughout European cities and Berlin, rather than solely focusing on wastewater, which will be led by Prototypes. Diversification of waste heat recovery will allow for competition and risk reduction.

Several barriers to market entry should be considered for this intervention. The web application will first need to create awareness about this potential solution within Berlin real estate communities to attract interest and build a larger portfolio of successful use cases. Second, the application will need to upgrade its analytical capabilities to identify high-potential buildings, which are depending on a variety of factors, including current energy sources and size. The ability to quickly and accurately assess heating demand in these high-potential buildings in an efficient manner will be critical to competing with the status quo of gas-fired heating, especially given existing geopolitical tensions that weaken the regular supply chain. Finally, the upfront costs of deployment of equipment (e.g. heat pumps and new heating systems) may be a barrier that hinders the attractiveness of waste heat recovery projects and therefore of the web application itself.

The monitoring of resource flow is central within Berlin's pilot intervention as it was identified as a key challenge to the development of waste heat recovery projects. In the case of this intervention, the connection between the Waste Heat Radar and REFLOW OS plays a key role for visualising buildings locations with high potential for the use of recovered waste heat from the sewer, and lays the ground for supply and demand matching and real-time monitoring. The web application will provide key insights that support the understanding of the metabolism of waste heat flows at the city-level.

4. CLUJ-NAPOCA PILOT

Introduction

The goal of the REFLOW Cluj-Napoca pilot is the improvement of the energy efficiency of public and residential buildings across the Romanian city. The pilot aims, within the REFLOW project, to assess the impact of the current measures taken to date by the city on the energy efficiency of selected buildings and to involve local stakeholders in implementing these measures. In parallel, the pilot aimed to stimulate different actors within the ecosystem to propose new innovative ideas regarding the integration of renewable energy sources while educating them on the city's circular economy strategy.

The Cluj-Napoca REFLOW Consortium includes the Municipality of Cluj-Napoca,²⁹ Aries Transilvania,³⁰ and the National Institute for Research and Development of Isotopic and Molecular Technologies (ITIM).³¹ While stakeholders involved in the project already work with other branches of the ecosystem, the main collaborators are coordinated by the Municipality and their ideas are part of the co-creation of policy at a local level. Specifically, Aries Transilvania was in charge of mapping the existing energy stakeholders (suppliers, distributors, solution-providers, policy makers, customers, researchers, and educators), and is also responsible for measures on awareness raising and competence-building around circularity aspects of energy efficiency and dissemination of the existing information and knowledge. The purpose was to bring together stakeholders that can contribute to the development of new ideas, and the testing of these within the pilot city.

²⁹ <https://primariaclujnapoca.ro/>

³⁰ <https://aries-transilvania.ro/>

³¹ <http://ro.itim-cj.ro/>

Figure 15. Energy use monitoring app.

Intervention: Retrofit Kit

Summary of the intervention

In the Deliverable D3.2, the Energy Flow Analysis (EFA) identified electricity consumption as the main contributor of CO₂ emissions from Cluj-Napoca’ public buildings. The pilot pursues the goal of increasing the energy efficiency in local public schools with the installation of a Retrofit Kit aiming to reduce energy consumption. Each Retrofit Kit solution allows for a targeted 15% reduction of electricity consumption once installed. The pilot includes the installation of a Retrofit Kit in the dormitory of the ‘Energetic’ High School in Cluj-Napoca. This location was strategically selected as the students are seen as possible multipliers of the principles and the practice of the Retrofit Kit. This encompasses a combination of five components: smart sockets (16), electric panels (6), motion sensors (40), LED lighting fixtures (145), and smart metering systems (10). The novelty does not lie in the individual components per se, but rather in the way they are combined into a package and present a highly versatile product. The installation of external hardware is perceived as an alternative to costly renovation in existing buildings to reduce electricity consumption.

Additionally, the pilot included a dashboard (see Figure 15) to provide an overview of energy consumption in the building along with energy efficiency and circularity recommendations. The smart metering system is also connected to the Open Data Dashboard where measured data are periodically sent for display (see Figure 15). Providing real-time feedback is a way to change behaviour and guide toward targeted interventions that should lead to reduced energy consumption.

The five-year goal

The Cluj-Napoca pilot has set the goal of scaling their Retrofit Kit intervention to cover a total of 15% of all municipal buildings. In buildings in which the kits will be installed, the goal is to reach, at least, a 15% reduction in electricity consumption.

Methodology

Baseline. To be able to conclude on environmental impact reduction of the intervention, a baseline scenario before the beginning of REFLOW was used. For the Retrofit Kit, the baseline analysis calculations were performed based on the 2019 actual electricity consumption data from the electricity provider Electrica Distributie Transilvania Nord at a specific point of consumption in the school building. The 2019 data was used instead of 2020 data in order to reduce effects the Covid-19 pandemic might have had on the data collected at the school dormitory. To better compare the impacts of the baseline scenario to those of the REFLOW intervention, the electricity consumption was retrieved on a monthly basis. The total electricity consumption for the baseline was measured for the months for which consumption data was available before and after the intervention. Hence, March was the first month used for the comparison since the Retrofit Kit was installed in February 2021, and November was the last one as no data was available for December 2019. For the two periods compared, June, July, and August were school holidays.

The environmental impacts from the consumption data collected, similarly as for the two other scenarios, were calculated based on the electricity mix³² and the environmental impacts of each electricity source in Cluj-Napoca.³³

Figure 16. Electricity mix in Cluj-Napoca

³² U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA). (2021). Dataset.

³³ Koffi, B., Duerr, A., Iancu, A., Kona, A., & Janssens-Maenhout, G. (2017). CoM Default Emission Factors for the Member States of the European Union - Version 2017 - Data Europa EU, from <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets/jrc-com-ef-comw-ef-2017?locale=en>

Intervention. The Cluj-Napoca pilot has installed a Retrofit Kit in one building of a local school in February 2021. The kit includes LED lighting fixtures, motion sensors, smart electrical panels, and smart sockets. The addition of this hardware aims to reduce the electricity consumption in the building. The electricity consumption saw an average decrease of 27%. To measure the reduction, the pilot has collected electricity consumption data from the same point of consumption as the one measured for the baseline period. The environmental impact calculations were performed using the electricity mix and its respective environmental impacts.

The energy consumption data before the intervention and after were used to calculate the environmental impacts and benefits related to the solution.

Five-year scenario. The intervention's results help to estimate the potential reduction of electricity consumption if scaling the solution to the five-year goal set by the pilot of applying the REFLOW protocol in 15% of municipal buildings (REFLOW Deliverable D5.3). As a result, the impact potentially avoided in Cluj-Napoca was calculated by retrieving the baseline electricity consumption of all municipal buildings from the EFA performed in the REFLOW deliverable D3.2. From this baseline electricity consumption, the potential energy consumption and the environmental impacts were calculated, assuming the percentage of electricity consumption reduction achieved within REFLOW would be similar for all buildings.

Results

Baseline. The baseline analysis yielded that original electricity consumption, measured at one point of consumption (POD) from March to November 2019, is 79.24 MWh. This consumption of electricity resulted in the emission of 13.5 tonnes of CO₂-eq based on the local electricity mix.

Intervention. The Cluj-Napoca pilot aimed to reduce its electricity consumption by 1 e same baseline period in 2019. This electricity consumption led to the emission of 9.91 tonnes of CO₂-eq, hence 3.6 tonnes of CO₂-eq were saved.

Five-year scenario. Within the next five years, the Cluj-Napoca pilot set a target to install the Retrofit Kit in 15% of all municipal buildings in the city. From the baseline analysis performed in the initial EFA, the total electricity consumption for all municipal buildings was 46,080 MWh/year, hence 6,912 MWh/year for 15% of the municipal buildings. This initial electricity consumption estimate would result in the emission of 1,160.1 tonnes of CO₂-eq. Assuming that the electricity consumption reduction follows the same trend after the installation of the kit as for the school dormitory (26.5% reduction), it is possible to estimate a total electricity consumption of 5,080 MWh/year for 15% of the municipal buildings. This consumption would yield in 853 tonnes of CO₂-eq, resulting in 308 tonnes of CO₂-eq avoided.

The benefits of the intervention, both on the short- and long-term, are highlighted below (see Table 7, Figure 17, and Figure 18).

Table 7. Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline, the intervention, and the scaled intervention for the Cluj-Napoca pilot.

Environmental Impacts	Baseline for the school dormitory (9 months)	Baseline for 15% of municipal buildings (1 year)	Intervention for the school dormitory (9 months)	Scaled intervention for 15% of municipal buildings (1 year)
Total energy consumption (MWH)	79.2	6,912.0	58.2	5,080.0
Total energy consumption avoided (MWH)	0	0	21.0	1,832.0
Total CO ₂ -eq emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	3.6	308

Figure 17. Electricity consumption comparison for the Cluj-Napoca pilot.

Figure 18. GHG emissions comparison for the Cluj-Napoca pilot.

Assumptions & Limitations

The measurements at the point of consumption (POD) were not representative of the dormitory specifically, but for the entirety of the building. This makes it difficult to measure the exact quantity of electricity avoided thanks to the Retrofit kit and to establish any causality between the intervention and the associated environmental impacts with confidence. Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic led to an unusual 2021 school year, which made it more difficult to compare with the 2019 baseline – the 2019 data was chosen over the 2020 in order to reduce those impacts even more. In terms of the long-term scenario, assumptions had to be made regarding the potential reduction from the kit in other municipal buildings. The assumption was that reduction would follow a similar trend as for the school dormitory, but that each building would likely present a different pattern based on the building typologies, the year of construction, the use, and other parameters.

Discussion on scaling and barriers to market entry and resource monitoring

The City of Cluj-Napoca has a large portfolio of public buildings ranging from schools, to nurseries, to administrative offices. With the majority of the total electricity, within the city's boundary, consumed from residential buildings, households, and municipal buildings, the latter present an interesting leverage point for the municipality to lower the environmental footprint of the city. The intervention developed by the Cluj-Napoca pilot tackles energy inefficiency of buildings, a recurring but solvable issue in Europe. This intervention can positively affect the overall urban metabolism of the city when scaled by reducing the required input of energy, which is still highly dependent on conventional and environmentally damaging sources. While minimising the energy consumption, resources are prevented from being used, hence adhering to the Reduce strategy of the circular economy framework.

The pilot achieved an electricity consumption reduction of 26.5% at the school dormitory, which is close to two times higher than their previous target of 15%. However, as it currently stands, the Retrofit Kit presents some barriers in terms of energy saving and impact potential. A standardised kit might not be adequate for any type of building. In fact, meticulous audits should be carried out before implementing energy saving intervention to identify the main causes of inefficiency. For older European buildings, recurring causes are often related to the building materials and design or to the systems component (e.g. heating, boiler, insulation). Upon completing each audit, the REFLOW pilot team would need to identify which assets their Retrofit Kit can contribute the most to. For those assets which the Retrofit Kit cannot support, additional energy efficiency upgrades should be identified. The Retrofit Kit, as it is currently laid out, would be a potential first step to implement in a few municipal buildings, however, the impacts might be minimal when compared to other sources of inefficiency. Another obstacle already encountered by the municipality in scaling up the Retrofit Kit is the initial costs - estimated at thousands of euros per building depending on the type. This specific solution was chosen for its potential electricity savings, given its lower cost than other more invasive interventions. However, a maximum return on investment for the municipality, as previously stated, might require other interventions and might require developing more solid partnerships with hardware suppliers.

For each REFLOW intervention, and to coordinate the recalibration of the local urban metabolism, the monitoring of resource flows represents a challenge and a barrier to be solved. In the case of this intervention, the development of the REFLOW OS dashboard can provide the foundation of circular monitoring. A key challenge resides in the principal actor monitoring the consumption. The Cluj-Napoca pilot does not directly have access to the consumption point data, which is measured by the electricity provider. Again, resulting from the third-party electricity measurement, the pilot does not have the capacity to have granular electricity consumption data and must adjust its impact calculation based on the measurements collected by the electricity distributor. The dependency on a large player such as the Electrica Distribuție Transilvania Nord distributor results in a more lengthy and less transparent data collection process for the electricity consumption of their assets and makes it more difficult to assess the impacts of the localised intervention.

5. MILAN PILOT

Introduction

The REFLOW Milan pilot focuses on supporting the transition of the city towards a circular food system for agrifood products, such as fruit, vegetables, cereals, meat, fish, and dairy through a series of activities around co-creation, co-design, and co-production.

To make this systemic change possible, the Milan pilot needed to develop a new way of operating within the value chain based on the tracking of materials and processes connected to the key players of the urban food system. Therefore, the Milan pilot's development pathway was founded on connecting a multitude of different actors in the urban food system, including large municipal enterprises, wholesalers, retailers, universities (Polimi³⁴), FabLabs (WeMake,³⁵ OpenDot,³⁶ Polifactory³⁷), citizens, and NGOs engaged in the fight against food waste, and allowing for possible paths of circular and social innovations to emerge from these collaborations. In the co-creation phase, workshops with key actors in the urban food system led to the co-creation of scenarios that set clear directions for all pilot activities and interventions. In practice, these interventions on the food flows were tested at different scales, looking at the flow through SoGeMi,³⁸ Milan's main food wholesale market, and the city's 23 covered municipal markets. Overall, two concrete and actionable axes became the focal points of the pilot:

- Food waste prevention and reduction in wholesaling markets
- Tracking food flows across local supply chains allowing them to be used further to create new value

While the full overview of activities of Milan pilots can be found in REFLOW Deliverable 1.5, this deliverable focuses on the food waste reduction intervention, aligning with the criteria described in the introduction of this deliverable (see Section 1.5). This intervention had direct environmental impacts and recorded enough data within the REFLOW period. In the future, although the nature of the impacts is indirect, after implementing the Food Market 4.0 or Prima Seconda interventions at a larger scale and monitoring the related avoided food waste, a similar assessment could be performed.

³⁴ <https://www.polimi.it/en/>

³⁵ <https://wemake.cc/>

³⁶ <https://www.opendotlab.it/>

³⁷ <https://www.polifactory.polimi.it/en/>

³⁸ <https://www.sogemispa.it/>

Intervention: Foody Zero Waste

Summary of the intervention

The use case focuses on the recovery of unsold fruit and vegetables within the Foody Hub market, managed by SoGeMi, and it has been developed in collaboration with SoGeMi, the food recovery association RECUP,³⁹ local NGOs such as the Italian Red Cross,⁴⁰ and selected wholesalers.

Despite the variety of initiatives in Milan working on reducing food waste within markets, shops, and restaurants, two challenges remain unsolved: a highly uncertain and varying supply (from the markets) and the demand (from NGOs, such as the Red Cross) for food products. Overall, the lack of communication among the involved stakeholders and of established recovery processes impedes these initiatives to achieve their full potential in recovering as much food as possible.

The Foody Zero Waste intervention focuses on optimising the communication and tracking of surplus food to the network of Milan food associations via the NGO RECUP, through the use of BOTTO. BOTTO is both an IoT technology device and a Telegram Bot that allows an automated communication to facilitate the reallocation of surplus fruit and vegetable products made available by SoGeMi wholesalers to selected stakeholders (such as RECUP). This solution helps address the unpredictable supply from markets - i.e. the type and the amount of food which varies greatly and the demand challenges the food recovery organisations face, by having a quick and real-time snapshot of the available food. Moreover, wholesalers do not need to struggle with coordinating their own food supply, as BOTTO allows for these actors to easily display their supply to a range of charity organisations – in this case, the Italian Red Cross during the piloting period – while also easily defining an agreement with them. Finally, Foody Zero Waste allows the wholesalers to reduce waste management expenses and improve their social and environmental sustainability.

The Foody Zero Waste solution was implemented with fruit and vegetable wholesalers, RECUP and the Italian Red Cross in February 2022 within the SoGeMi market. The BOTTO device was distributed to wholesalers to indicate the food surplus (see Figure 20).

³⁹ <https://associazionerecup.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://cri.it/>

Figure 19. BOTTO is composed of an IoT technology device and a Telegram Bot, which allow both wholesalers and NGOs to interact with one other.

Figure 20. Life-cycle stages of the Foody Zero Waste intervention.

The five-year goal

The Milan pilot has a five-year goal to deploy its food waste recovery protocol, including the BOTTO hardware and software systems across all SoGeMi wholesale markets and Milan's 23 municipal covered markets, to drastically reduce food waste through optimised re-distribution channels. Due to a lack of data from the covered markets, it was not possible to calculate an estimate of this solution should it scale, and as result it made reliable data projection too difficult for a meaningful assessment. Nonetheless, this goal still provides a main point of reference to anticipate the impacts of the expansion of the solution within Milan's urban metabolism.

Methodology

Production Stage

Baseline. For the Foody Zero Waste intervention, RECUP provided data for the whole 2021 year. The baseline analysis calculations were performed using a rough breakdown of product types saved by RECUP and their quantities for the exact same period as the 2022 test phase (four weeks in February) and average values of CO₂-eq, water depletion, and land use impacts. To better compare the impacts of the baseline scenario to those of the REFLOW intervention, the total impacts avoided were calculated thanks to the total amount of food recovered during the baseline period. Recovering food products helps avoid the production of new food products to fulfil the existing demand, and allow for the impacts that already occurred during the production of these food items not to be produced unnecessarily. The total quantity of the food products recovered were multiplied by the per-kg impacts which provided a total environmental impact for each scenario (see Equation 1).

The Foody Zero Waste solution was implemented with fruit and vegetable wholesalers, RECUP and the Italian Red Cross in February 2022 within the SoGeMi market. The BOTTO device was distributed to wholesalers to indicate the food surplus (see Figure 20).

Equation 1.

$$\text{Total Impact Avoided} = \text{Quantity of food items}_{\text{aggregated}} * \text{Impact}_{\text{averaged}}$$

Table 8. Environmental impacts of production of the baseline scenario for four collections in February 2021 (Source: RECUP & RIVM⁴¹)

Produces	Food saved (kg)	Production GHG emissions (kg CO ₂ -eq/kg)	Production water depletion (m ³ /kg)	Production land use (m ² /kg)
Bananas, Clementines, Strawberries, chard, Celery, radish	1,457	1.90	0.19	0.67
Bananas, radish, chard	770	0.71	0.07	0.58
Iceberg lettuce, blackberries, strawberries, beet, chicory	632	2.52	0.16	0.46
Zucchini, broccoli, cucumbers, pumpkins, chard, chicory, turnip, iceberg lettuce	676	1.11	0.06	0.53

Intervention. By increasing the total recovery of food products, the Foody Zero Waste intervention is helping to avoid even more new production of food products. The ‘avoided’ production impacts are therefore calculated by 1) quantifying the weighted average impact per kg of food items collected each week for CO₂-eq emitted, water use (m³), and land use (m²) during the production stage (cradle to farm gate)(see Equation 2), and 2) multiplying the weighted average by the total amounts of food items recovered each week of the test phase (see Table 9 and Equation 3). For each week of the test phase, the food collected was variable, hence a weighted average was calculated for each and multiplied by the quantity collected per week.

Equation 2.

$$\text{Weighted average impact per kg of food} = \frac{\sum (\text{Food mass share} * \text{Food impactn})}{\sum (\text{Food mass share})}$$

⁴¹ <https://www.rivm.nl/voedsel-en-voeding/duurzaam-voedsel/database-milieubelasting-voedingsmiddelen>

Table 9. Environmental impacts of production of the intervention for four collections in February 2021 (Source: Dutch RVIM⁴²)*

Type of produce (aggregated)	Food saved (kg)	Production GHG emissions (kg CO ₂ -eq/kg)	Production water depletion (m ³ /kg)	Production land use (m ² /kg)
Leaf vegetables	3,024	0.69	0.05	0.56
Other vegetables	2,223	2.20	0.10	0.67
Exotic fruit	946	1.00	0.14	0.83
Root vegetables	762	0.53	0.04	0.53
Apples and pears	637	0.69	0.05	0.56
Citrus fruit	436	1.00	0.14	0.83
Onions and garlic	335	0.45	0.02	0.36
Other fresh fruit	255	2.20	0.10	0.67
Herbs	48	0.69	0.05	0.56
Tomatoes	35	1.20	0.20	1.20
Berries	2	0.69	0.05	0.56

* See appendices for a detailed list of the products recovered by RECUP during the test period.

Equation 3.

$$\text{Total avoided impact} = \text{Weighted average impact} * \text{Mass food saved}$$

⁴² RVIM (2020) Milieubelasting van voedingsmiddelen | RIVM. <https://www.rivm.nl/voedsel-en-voeding/duurzaam-voedsel/database-milieubelasting-voedingsmiddelen>

End-of-Life Stage

Baseline & Intervention. Thanks to the food recovery activities, the food products saved are redirected to be consumed and therefore avoid the traditional waste treatment channels of the city. The avoided impacts of the treatment process are calculated. In Milan, food is treated through anaerobic digestion (REFLOW Deliverable D3.2). The anaerobic digestion impacts for all food products of 0.106 kg CO₂-eq/kg was retrieved from the Ecoinvent 3.8 life-cycle inventory and assessment database.

Equation 4.

$$\text{Total impact AD} = \text{Total mass of food saved} * \text{AD impact}$$

Results

Baseline. The analysis of the baseline yielded that during the same four-week period as the testing phase, 3.1 tonnes of food were saved, which resulted in avoiding the unnecessary emissions of a total of 6 tonnes of CO₂-eq. Overall this quantity of food saved used 5.6 tonnes CO₂-eq, 465 m³ of water, and 2,074 m² of land during its production process. These impacts would have been emitted unnecessarily without RECUP's work, whereas they are now redirected to vulnerable communities. The anaerobic digestion of these food products would have caused 0.37 tonnes of CO₂-eq emission, contributing to local air pollution in Milan – although it would have contributed to the production of biogas (renewable energy) and compost.

Intervention. The analysis of the intervention yielded that during the 4-week testing period of the BOTTO device, a total of 8.7 tonnes of food was recovered successfully leading to a total of 10.8 tonnes of CO₂-eq. avoided. The recovery of food products has increased by almost 170% compared to the baseline period that occurred during the same period in the year. This amount of food saved represented 10 tonnes of CO₂-eq emitted, 653 m³ of water, and 5,436 m² of land used during the production of these food products. Concerning the end-of-life impacts, if the food would have been anaerobically digested, this would have caused the emissions of almost 0.9 tonnes of CO₂-eq. contributing to local pollution. Thanks to the intervention, these unnecessary impacts were avoided.

The benefits of the intervention are highlighted below (see Table 10, Figure 21, and Figure 22).

Table 10. Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline and the intervention for the Foody Zero Waste intervention.

Environmental impacts	Baseline	Intervention
Total quantity of food saved (tonnes)	3.1	8.7
Total CO ₂ -eq emissions avoided (tonne)	6.0	10.8
Total water depletion avoided (m ³)	465	522
Total land use avoided (m ²)	5,000	4,427

Figure 21. Food saved comparison for the Foody Zero Waste intervention.

Figure 22. GHG emissions avoided for the Foody Zero Waste intervention.

Assumptions and limitations

Several limitations should be considered regarding the assessment of the environmental impacts for the Foody Zero Waste intervention. The test period of three weeks was the only period that could be compared with the 2021 annual baseline. The timing of the implementation of the intervention came just slightly prior to the environmental assessment which did not allow collection for a longer period of time. Due to the seasonality of the products and the variability observed in the previous year for each month, it is difficult to effectively produce a yearly estimate based on the three-weeks period.

Finally, the calculation of the production impacts was based on impacts developed for more generic types of products provided by the Dutch National Institute for Health and the Environment. For higher precision and specificity for the Italian context, it would be required to perform more local studies on the life-cycle stages of each product.

Discussion on scaling, barriers to market entry, and resource monitoring

The Milan pilot has set food waste as a core focus for the transition of the city's food system towards circularity. In the second year of REFLOW (Deliverable D3.2) it was established that despite the presence of initiatives to reduce food waste through food recovery and re-distribution efforts, only 16% of the unsold fruits and vegetables were recovered while the rest ended up in the organic waste bin. These food initiatives, such as RECUP, face recurrent challenges both in terms of unpredictable and fast-changing supply from markets and the demand from NGOs as well as difficulty in communicating and coordinating with food donors. The intervention developed by the Milan pilot, if scaled to reach its five-year goal of 23 covered markets of the city, can have a major influence on the flows of recovered food. In terms of order of magnitude, unsold food products throughout the year from SoGeMi (Italy's and one of Europe's largest fruits and vegetable wholesaling markets) and the 23 markets amount to thousands of tonnes (9,150 tonnes for SoGeMi alone). By optimising their recovery through BOTTO communication device, hundreds of tonnes may additionally be saved and re-distributed to people-in-need and across Milan's food deserts. As a result, the pilot intervention will have a beneficial effect on Milan's metabolism by rerouting and optimising the city's internal flows. More broadly, it will also strengthen the local food system, contributing to the growth of food re-distribution channels, and connecting better food donors, food collectors, NGOs, and food insecure communities. The latter will benefit the most as an increased amount of food can be re-directed towards them to meet their dietary needs.

Several barriers to market entry must be considered for the food recovery protocol. First, the lack of space in the infrastructures where the food is collected (wholesaling markets, covered markets) is a key barrier for the food recovery operations and the success of the optimisation process initiated by the intervention. With an increased flow of food products being recovered thanks to BOTTO, space is required to temporarily store the products and for sorting operations. Directly connected to the space requirement is the current lack of cold storage facilities that food recovery organisations could use to store their recovered products optimally. Vegetables and fruits are highly perishable (especially in spring and summer temperatures) and therefore may necessitate being kept refrigerated to lengthen their shelf life, and reach final consumers in an edible state. Thus, infrastructural challenges must be addressed in order to enable Milan's intervention to scale successfully. Finally, the incentivisation of food waste donation remains a challenge in fast-paced food logistics where time is of the essence. The incentivisation element is directly related to the business model adopted by RECUP which still remains to be fully developed.

The monitoring of resource flow is central within Milan's pilot intervention. This was identified as a key challenge by local partners such as SoGeMi and RECUP and led to the development of the Foody Zero Waste approach with the BOTTO communication device. In the case of this intervention, the connection between BOTTO and REFLOW OS plays a key role for tracking and record-keeping, and overall will support the understanding of the metabolism of food flows at the wholesale-level and in the future at covered markets. This will provide unprecedented granular insights in terms of waste patterns, seasonality, and food types that are the most and least likely to be wasted.

Material development research outputs

Alternative Food Waste Applications

Developed in T3.2, the material development research has focused on biomaterial derived from food waste in Milan. The potential production of biomaterials using the unavoidable food waste (UFW)⁴³ produced at the city level every year was analysed to assess the potential reuse of local and abundant resources that are currently considered waste, without competing with edible waste. The food waste analysis model developed by Metabolic (Coudard et al., 2021)⁴⁴ allowed the analysis of the availability of biopolymers suitable for material production (see Appendices). From this analysis, four relevant biopolymers for the creation of biomaterials were determined, namely, cellulose, starch, gelatin and chitin. The first three were selected because of the high abundance of this polymer, which would facilitate the scaling-up of future production. However Chitin, although not present in large quantities in the model, was selected because of its great value as a resource for the manufacture of materials due to their mechanical properties and general low solubility, which are critical attributes for films, gels, and fibre materials.⁴⁵

Taking this into account, and because the pilot intends to continue working in this area with designers and creatives, it was decided to provide them with a set of swatches of the material systems developed. Additionally, this was complemented with a Material Development report explaining the criteria of the materials, how to replicate them, and the testing of their mechanical properties. With these resources, it is expected to facilitate the work of Milan and its stakeholders for the future manufacture and application of biomaterials, such as in initiatives like Centrinno H2020 EU project.⁴⁶ Finally, these resources will also be available to the other pilots, and the swatches were also sent to Amsterdam and Vejle, given their interest in bio-based materials.

⁴³ Inedible by-products that are an unavoidable part of production, such as peels, animal hides, seeds, etc.

⁴⁴ Coudard et al. (2021). Global water and energy losses from consumer avoidable food waste. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129342>

⁴⁵ Marguerite Rinaudo, 2006. Chitin and chitosan: Properties and applications. Progress in Polymer Science, Volume 31, Issue 7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2006.06.001>

⁴⁶ <https://centrinno.eu/>

6. PARIS

Introduction

The REFLOW Paris pilot focuses on city-wide timber and wood use in the temporary construction industry, including events – which was shown to be a large fraction of the wood waste generated (see Deliverable 3.2). The pilot sets out to quantify and qualify the waste material flows generated from such temporary use, through the development of new models and digital tools. These tools are aimed at facilitating the reuse of wood materials and products in order to contribute to the acceleration of circular models in this sector.

The pilot prototypes and tests digital tracking and scanning tools that leverage computational design techniques in their incubator, Driven x REFLOW.⁴⁷ By identifying and quantifying these material flows, wood can be monitored and reintegrated into manufacturing processes, extending the material life cycle. Besides this track-and-trace function, these tools are capable of generating databases of wood products. The goal of this inventory is to support the development of an agile digital marketplace that will increase material exchange between the events industry and the temporary construction sector.

From the two main Paris use cases developed in the Deliverable 5.3, the RE-Label and the Dimension-use, only the environmental impacts of the latter were assessed in this deliverable. According to the criteria described within the introduction of this deliverable (see Section 1.5), the RE-Label solution did not have a direct environmental impact, which jointly with little data available, made too difficult a meaningful environmental impact assessment.

⁴⁷ <https://drivenbyvolumes.io/>

Intervention: Foody Zero Waste

Summary of the intervention

The Dimension-use is a semi-automated scanner for different materials (such as timber/wood in Paris) that collects material-specific data and makes it available to a variety of users to promote reuse. The collected data (through the scanning device) is visible in an online database which facilitates the further use (REFLOW OS). The scanner creates a digital inventory but does not manage it. Therefore, it is connected to another system (inventory management system or another reuse marketplace). The customer can scan their wood (which they do not have further use for) and the database shows and provides it to potential next users.

Within the timeline of the REFLOW project, the pilot was able to implement the Dimension-use system during the September 2021 Maison&Objet⁴⁸ event. The wood collected from the exhibitors, totalling 3.5 tonnes, was scanned through the Dimension-use, which provides a material database for designing for flexibility (Figure 23). From the wood collected, new modular furniture was designed by WAO,⁴⁹ a French architecture firm, to first serve as exhibition stands in the March 2022 Maison&Objet edition (postponed due to COVID-19 from January 2022), and to later be transformed as office furniture in the coworking space of the new Fab City Paris Hub (see Figure 24). Within this use case, the Paris pilot team covers a role as a Paris SAS⁵⁰ which operates by providing consulting activities, facilitating reuse, and as well as connecting actors in the network of REFLOW.

Figure 23. Dimension-use system used during the intervention.

⁴⁸ <https://www.maison-objet.com/en/paris>

⁴⁹ <https://wao.paris/>

⁵⁰ SAS refers to société par actions simplifiée which is a type of business entity in France.

Figure 24. Wood collected and modular constructions.

The five-year goal

The Paris pilot aims to replicate the REFLOW protocol through other large events where the wooden materials are not currently reused. From a first event, the materials would be collected to be reused at one more event and then remodelled into more permanent furniture to lengthen the materials' useful life. The Paris pilot's goal is to develop the protocol implemented at Maison&Objet in five large-scale events in the city within five years from the end of the REFLOW project.

Figure 25. Life-cycle stages of the REFLOW intervention.

Methodology

The Paris pilot uses the Dimension-use to characterise the materials they collect after a first event to facilitate the reuse in newly-designed modular furniture for the next edition of the event and then for use in local co-working spaces. To determine the environmental impacts avoided from the implementation of the solution, materials are assumed to be used in three settings, all of which would have required production and end-of-life treatment if the intervention had not been implemented. With the intervention, the production and end-of-life treatments must take place once, and are avoided twice from the reuse in two additional settings (Figure 25). The collection, redesign, and reassembling steps were omitted from the environmental impact calculations as they are quite negligible as compared to the production and end-of-life impacts.

Production Stage

Baseline & Intervention. During the first Maison&Objet event (September 2021), the pilot collected a total 3.49 tonnes of wood – 2.70 tonnes of plywood, 0.48 tonnes of MDF, 0.14 tonnes of oriented strand board (OSB), and 0.18 tonnes of pine. For the production impacts of each of the wood products, the respective per unit production impacts were multiplied by the total amount of each and by two as the production is avoided twice (see equation 1). For the different types of wood collected – MDF, plywood, pine, and OSB – the production stage’s impacts were retrieved from the Ecoinvent 3.8 LCA database (see Table 11).

Equation 1.

$$\text{Total avoided production impact} = \sum(\text{Quantity of wood}_n * \text{Production impact}_n * 2)$$

Table 11. Environmental impacts of production stage of different wood products (Source: Ecoinvent 3.8).

Wood type	Wood recovered (tonnes)	Production GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂ -eq/tonne)	Production human toxicity (tonnes 1,4-DCB-eq/tonne)
Plywood	2.700	0.77	0.50
MDF	0.484	0.82	0.38
OSB	0.138	0.40	0.30
Pine	0.177	0.06	0.02

End-of-life Stage

Baseline & Intervention. The end-of-life impacts avoided by the REFLOW intervention were calculated based on the same quantities collected during the first Maison&Objet event. For the baseline, it was assumed that all the wood used at the Maison&Objet events was collected by Valdelia,⁵¹ an event waste collector, after use. Therefore, all materials were produced for a one-time event and then processed according to the Valdelia value chain: incineration, recycling, landfill, and reuse (see Table 12). For each of the treatments, the respective per unit impacts were multiplied by the total amount of waste wood and multiplied again by two. The end-of-life treatments are avoided twice since the materials are used in two subsequent events, and then transformed into furniture (see Equation 2). For the intervention, the end-of-life stage was avoided altogether by refitting the wood material into furniture for long-term use.

Equation 2.

$$\text{Total avoided EOL impacts} = \text{Quantity of waste wood} * \sum(\text{EoL treatment share} * \text{Impact of the EoL treatment}) * 2$$

Table 12. Waste routes and environmental impacts of wood products waste treatment (Source: Ecoinvent 3.8)

End-of-life treatment	Baseline treatment weight (%)	End-of-life GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂ -eq/tonne)	End-of-life human toxicity (tonnes 1,4 DCB-eq/tonne)
Waste wood incineration	7	0.013	0.050
Waste wood recycling	83	0.045	0.014
Waste wood landfill	9	0.077	0.060
Waste wood reuse	1	0.000	0.000

⁵¹ <https://www.valdelia.org/>

Five-year scenario. Based on the intervention's result, the potential reduction of the scaled solution to the five-year goal set by the pilot (REFLOW Deliverable D5.3) was calculated. In the next five-years, the pilot plans on applying this protocol for five other large events in Paris while doubling the collection capacity. The potential environmental impact reduction was simply calculated by proportionally scaling the impacts avoided during REFLOW for 3.49 tonnes collected to a total of 35.00 tonnes within five-years.

Results

Intervention. The analysis of the intervention yielded that the recovery of 3.49 tonnes of wood from the Maison&Objet event would help avoid the emissions of about 5.10 tonnes CO₂-eq during the production of virgin wood products. Additionally, about 3.15 tonnes of 1,4DCB-eq would be saved from the production.

Concerning the end-of-life impacts, should the majority of the 3.49 tonnes of wood (83%) be recycled, while the rest be divided between incineration, landfill, and reuse, this would cause the emissions of almost 0.27 tonnes of CO₂-eq and 0.173 tonnes of 1,4DCB-eq contributing to local pollution. Thanks to the Dimension-use and the REFLOW protocol, these impacts will be avoided. Despite the positive effects of Valdelia's collection process compared to the usual incineration of waste, increasing the share of reused materials would avoid much larger environmental impacts related to production and end-of-life treatment.

In total, the emissions of about 5.37 tonnes of CO₂-eq and 3.32 tonnes of 1,4DCB-eq are avoided through this intervention.

Five-year scenario. Within the next five years, the Paris pilot has set a target to recover 35 tonnes of wood items through the deployment of the Dimension-use and REFLOW protocol in five large-scale events in Paris. These 35 tonnes will be recovered to be reused through another temporary event and then in an office set-up (Fig. 24). The deployment of this solution to this scale would therefore lead to avoiding the emissions of about 50.98 tonnes of CO₂-eq and 31.48 1,4DCB-eq during the wood production processes.

Concerning the end-of-life impacts, should the majority of the 35 tonnes of wood (83%) be recycled, while the rest be divided between incineration, landfill, and reuse, this would cause the emissions of almost 2.74 tonnes of CO₂-eq. and 1.73 tonnes of 1,4DCB-eq. Thanks to the Dimension-use and the REFLOW protocol, these impacts will be avoided.

In total, the emissions of about 53.72 tonnes of CO₂-eq and 33.22 tonnes of 1,4DCB-eq are avoided with the intervention. Thus, the vast majority of environmental benefits lie in the avoided production impacts upstream in the supply chain.

The benefits of the intervention, both on the short- and long-term, are highlighted below (see Table 13, Figure 26, and Figure 27).

Table 13. Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline and the intervention of the Dimension-use intervention.

Environmental impacts	Baseline	Baseline for scaled intervention	Intervention	Scaled intervention
Raw material production (tonnes)	10.47	105	3.49	35
Raw material production avoided (tonnes)	0	0	6.98	70
Wood diverted from recycling, landfill, and incineration (tonnes)	0	0	6.98	70
Total CO ₂ -eq emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	5.37	53.72
Total 1,4DCB-eq emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	3.32	33.22

Figure 26. Raw material use comparison for the Dimension-use intervention.

Figure 27. GHG emissions comparison for the Dimension-use intervention.

Assumptions and limitations

The impacts avoided from the implementation of the Dimension-use use case in the Maison&Objet setting were estimated assuming consistent end-of-life treatments following Valdelia’s average treatment breakdown. In reality, depending on the events in which the REFLOW protocol will be implemented, the wood waste collection might differ and show different impacts. Ideally, it may be expected that the fraction of wood reused at the end of the wood product’s useful life would increase and that the REFLOW protocol could even be repeated after using the products in a long-term setting.

Moreover, it is critical to note that the wood type breakdown is not representative of the wood waste from the Maison&Objet event, but represents the selection of wood collected for reuse by the Paris pilot. A larger impact reduction could be achieved in the scenario where a larger quantity of MDF would be collected, the material having the largest environmental footprint, compared to the other wood types. Unfortunately, this type of wood, largely present in the event sector, does not currently present good reuse and remanufacturing opportunities.

Discussion on scaling and barriers to market entry and resource monitoring

The City of Paris is a cultural hub in Europe and is the home of a large number of cultural events. From the analysis of the wood waste generated throughout the city performed under REFLOW D3.2, it was highlighted that the events and cultural centres are the producers of more than 24 kilo-tonnes per year. After their short use, the wooden products used within this sector can quickly see their value decrease while they are downscaled through recycling, incineration, or disposed of in landfills. The intervention developed by the pilot is a proof of the large potential for reuse of wood materials from the temporary sector event. The small-scale Dimension-use technological tool helped the pilot to reuse a considerable number of products while showcasing the potential for reuse in a different setting, as well as engaging multiple stakeholders in the process. The five-year goal set by the pilot could have a significant impact as the Dimension-use is scaled up to five large-scale events. Indeed, Paris' urban ecosystem could greatly benefit from the pilot in multiple spheres of its diverse event sector. From the world's largest cultural productions to the 2024 Paris Summer Olympics, the possibilities for showcasing and communicating the new technology are endless. The integration of the REFLOW intervention within those settings would promote a local ecosystem connection between a wide range of different stakeholders (e.g. architects, designers, workshops, waste managers, exhibitors, event organisers, offices, and businesses).

As it currently stands, the solution presents some challenges that should be considered when scaling up. A notable hurdle when it comes to collecting materials is within logistics. Collecting, scanning, storing, and managing materials requires an efficient workflow to remain within the time constraints imposed by the steady environment of the event sector. Physical space is critical in European cities, especially in Paris, which makes it difficult for the integration of a larger scale Dimension-use tool and for the storage of the materials. For the smooth integration and use of the intervention, monitoring of all materials used in the temporary event sector could become a norm and be fulfilled by each organisation (e.g. event organisers, exhibitors, businesses). A concept similar to extending producer responsibility could be integrated to make it the responsibility of the material users to find a reuse pathway (internally or externally) for their materials. Instead of remodelling the modular furniture to a more fixed setting after the use in one other temporary event, it could be imagined that the materials are reused year after year for the same exhibition by the same actors or event after event by multiple users.

For the Dimension-use intervention, the monitoring of resource flows represents a key challenge, as previously mentioned, but could also unlock multiple opportunities for reuse by local actors. In the case of this intervention, the development of REFLOW OS can provide the foundation of circular monitoring, helping track the wooden products in use or stored within the city. A key challenge that will need to be addressed will be the buy-in of the event sector actors that may not currently see the added value from their business-as-usual practice. Awareness about the benefits of using the monitoring system will need to be raised through campaigns, demonstrations, and sharing of best practices. The monitoring of the used materials will allow more transparency on the state of the materials, the cost benefits, and the dimensions.

7. VEJLE PILOT

Introduction

The REFLOW Vejle pilot focused on gaining insights into urban plastic consumption and, at the same time, increasing the circularity of the city's plastic value chains. The accumulation of non-recyclable plastic, plastic-based waste, and its poor management are a recurrent problem for any European cities and their waste department.⁵² Vejle is no exception. The Reflow program enabled the pilot to gain valuable insights into the Danish city's bottlenecks of plastic use and recycling behaviour by working closely with various actors, including retailers, manufacturers, citizens, healthcare facilities, and innovation centres. The pilot project took place in Vestbyen, the Western neighbourhood of the city, where the pilot project ran targeted experimentations, workshops, and engagement sessions to identify and showcase solutions for increased plastic reuse, recovery, and reduction with local communities. Additionally, the pilot included three other initiatives targeting the private and public sectors. The first was for a retail store in the supermarket chain REMA 1000,⁵³ where the pilot focused on creating circular streams of specific plastic types by prototyping new circular loops for specific plastic containers and scaling this to the rest of REMA 1000 stores in Denmark, as well as to other retailers in Denmark and the Nordics. Second, a public housing block called Den Gamle Gård,⁵⁴ is where the pilot focused on raising awareness and creating better and more intuitive sorting systems and information in apartment buildings, by engaging citizens and building a local community. Third, the public elderly home Sofiegården,⁵⁵ is where the pilot focused on changing the plastic stream in the healthcare sector, by prototyping new solutions that decreased the use of plastic.

⁵² https://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_EEF_Followup.pdf

⁵³ <https://rema1000.dk/>

⁵⁴ <http://www.dengamlegaard-stubberup.dk/>

⁵⁵ <https://sofiegaarden.vejle.dk/>

Intervention 1: REMA 1000

Summary of the intervention

The use case consists of reducing plastic waste at a REMA 1000 supermarket, one of the pilot's test-sites. The analysis of the waste stream at REMA 1000 in Vejle, performed within D3.3, highlighted that a total of 13.5% of the mixed waste is composed of plastic waste that has the potential to be recycled, mainly composed of candy buckets, unsold packaged food, and plastic bags.

As a result, the pilot made it its objective to generate and optimise better sorting through increased knowledge of waste sorting, with its Value Chain Mapping Game – connected to the REFLOW OS– and through the implementation of adapted workflows with the Renewed Sorting System for Food Retailers, where the pilot has started the process to implement the new legislation in Denmark of sorting the waste in ten waste types fractions.

The use case and the proposed solutions are developed in a co-creation process with the REMA 1000 management, a local REMA 1000 store in Vejle, the public waste management in Vejle and private operators. The use case imagines a longer term scaling up to all REMA 1000 stores in Denmark (approximately 350 stores), and later on to the entire Reitan Group in Northern Europe (approximately 1,900 stores).

In fact, within the REFLOW timeline, the pilot was able to divert 50% of the plastic waste previously sent for incineration, which amounts to about 33 kg of plastic recovered per week. From this plastic recovered, the majority is composed of hard plastic flower buckets and candy buckets, while the remaining plastic waste is mostly composed of unrecyclable plastic bags.

The five-year goal

The Vejle pilot has set itself a five-year goal to scale the REFLOW plastic sorting protocol to all seven Vejle's REMA 1000 stores.

Figure 28. Life-cycle stages of the REMA 1000 use case.

Methodology

Baseline. For the REMA 1000 use case, the baseline analysis calculations were performed based on the 2020 waste composition study data which highlighted that most of the plastic found in the waste stream at the REMA 1000 store represents food packaging (PE/PP), whereas another small portion represents plastic bags (LDPE). The baseline scenario implies that all of the plastic, totalling nearly 3.5 tonnes, was sent for incineration in Denmark (Figure 28).

As the recyclable plastic found in the waste is only differentiated between food packaging and plastic bags, for the food packaging, the environmental impacts of food packaging were averaged between the PE and PP types (see Equation 1).

Equation 1.

$$\text{Total end-of-life impacts} = \text{Quantity of waste food packaging} * (\text{impacts of PE} + \text{impacts PP}) / 2 + \text{Quantity of waste plastic bags} * \text{impacts of LDPE}$$

Table 14. Environmental impacts of plastics end-of-life treatments.

End-of-life treatment	End-of-life GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂ -eq/tonne)	End-of-life human toxicity (tonnes 1,4 DCB-eq/tonne)
PE/LDPE recycling	0.36	0.12
PP recycling	0.36	0.12
PE/LDPE incineration	3.02	0.57
PP incineration	2.55	0.48

Intervention. The Vejle pilot has performed another waste composition study after the implementation of the REFLOW protocol. A diminution of plastic of about 50% was observed in the waste stream, where most of the plastic left consisted of plastic bags and unrecyclable plastics (LDPE and mixed plastics) and where the plastic diverted consisted mostly of flower buckets and trays, and candy buckets (PE and PP).

The end-of-life impacts were calculated for both the plastics collected for recycling and for the one remaining in the mixed waste. Once again, as the exact proportion of plastic types both in the waste and recycled are partially unknown, averages of environmental impacts were used (see Equation 2).

Equation 2.

$$\text{Total EOL impacts} = \text{Quantity of plastic bags} * \text{impacts of LDPE} + \text{Quantity of mixed plastics} * (\text{impacts of PE} + \text{impacts PP}) / 2$$

Five-year scenario. Based on the intervention's results, it was possible to determine the potential reduction of the scaled solution to the five-year goal set by the pilot (REFLOW Deliverable D5.3). In the next five-years, the pilot plans on applying this protocol at all seven REMA 1000 stores in Vejle. The potential environmental impact reduction was simply calculated by proportionally scaling the impacts avoided during REFLOW for 3.43 tonnes collected yearly to a total of 24.01 tonnes within five-years.

Results

Baseline. Before the installation of the Sorting System at the REMA 1000 store, the 3.43 tonnes of plastic found in the waste stream were at the origin of the emission of 9.69 tonnes of CO₂-eq, and 1.82 tonnes of 1,4-DCB-eq.

Intervention. The analysis of the intervention yielded that the recovery of 1.72 tonnes of plastic from the one REMA 1000 store in Vejle helps avoid the emissions of about four tonnes CO₂-eq from saving 50% of the plastic waste from incineration to be recycled instead. Additionally, about 0.67 tonnes 1,4-DCB are avoided which decreases the impacts of human toxicity near the end-of-life treatment infrastructures.

Five-year scenario. Within the next five years, the Vejle pilot has set a target to divert about 24 tonnes of plastic from incineration through the deployment of the REFLOW protocol in seven REMA 1000 stores in Vejle. Following the same methodology used to assess the intervention impacts, the deployment of this solution to this scale would lead to avoiding the emissions of about 27.96 tonnes of CO₂-eq during the plastic waste end-of-life treatments, as well as the use of emission of about 4.66 tonnes of 1,4-DCB.

The benefits of the intervention, both on the short- and long-term, are highlighted below (see Table 15, Figure 29, and Figure 30).

Table 15. Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline and the intervention of the REMA 1000 use case

Environmental impacts	Baseline	Baseline for scaled intervention	Intervention	Scaled intervention
Plastic incinerated (tonnes)	3.43	24	1.72	12.04
Plastic recycled (tonnes)	0	0	1.72	12.04
Total CO ₂ -eq emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	3.99	27.93
Total 1,4-DCB emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	0.67	4.66

Figure 29. Plastic waste comparison for REMA 1000.

Figure 30. GHG emissions comparison for REMA 1000.

Assumptions and limitations

The environmental impacts avoided at the REMA 1000 store in Vejle were calculated based on a few key assumptions. In relation to the life-cycle stages studied, the assumption was that the production phase did not change after implementing the recycling system. In a further stage, when the capacity and the logistics would allow it, the recycled plastic products could potentially be directed to the production of the same product or packaging to better close the loop. Some of the products, such as the flower buckets, were partially reused, which was not accounted for in the scope of these calculations as the quantity is now variable and very limited.

Additionally, the transportation of the plastic waste to the recycling plants was not included in the assessment. Should the plastic be sent abroad, with fossil-fuel based transportation, it could reduce the overall benefits stemming from recycling.

To accommodate for the absence of data and the ability to model the impact of the intervention, the scaling potential of the intervention was calculated assuming that the waste quantity, recycling potential, and plastic composition remained unchanged within the different stores. In reality, the waste generated and its composition might slightly differ, depending on the location of the store (e.g. the context of the neighbourhood it is located in) and its capacity. It could be argued that over the years, the recycling capacity would see an increase due to logistical and behavioural improvements.

The impacts calculated could be slightly larger than the ones calculated if the packaged food (organic waste), for which the plastic packaging was not accounted for in the waste composition studies, was recovered to be further valorised through anaerobic digestion (organic) and recycling (plastic packaging).

Discussion on scaling and barriers to market entry and resource monitoring

The city of Vejle had the objective to get insights into urban plastic consumption and to increase the circularity of plastic flow. From the analysis of the plastic waste generated throughout the city – performed within REFLOW (REFLOW D3.2) – it was highlighted that 66% of plastics from businesses and industries is sent to incineration. Mostly being used for packaging, the actual life of the plastics in this sector is relatively short, which emphasises the importance of developing alternatives and of adopting adequate end-of-life processes. The intervention developed by the pilot at REMA 1000 directly targets the end-of-life management of the plastic waste found in a supermarket. The 50% diversion of plastic waste from incineration within the REFLOW project showcases the potential impact of the intervention should it be implemented at a larger scale. In addition, sorting presents a relatively easy-to-implement additional intervention that presents large potential to minimise environmental impacts. Within five years, the effects could already be considerable with the scaling within all the REMA 1000 stores in the city, but an even larger potential remains within the partnership with a wide range of businesses and industries. This positive case study should act as a testament to get other actors of the urban metabolism onboard and stimulate capacity building.

The solution, as it is currently designed, requires a large capacity building effort to enable its scaling across multiple stores in the city. Employees of all stores should be trained to adequately sort plastics to avoid contamination and optimise the results from the implementation of the intervention. To facilitate the local recycling of plastics, the intervention should be adopted on a larger scale across the urban metabolism which could give life to a local market for recycling. The end-of-life solution proposed here should be paired with front-end solutions, such as the use of bio-based plastic alternatives or promoting reuse. Reducing the production of plastic packaging at the source should become a priority, combined with their proposed intervention, to reduce the city's environmental impacts. This solution only captures the plastic packaging rejected at the retail level. However, it should not be forgotten that the largest stream of plastics in residual waste consists of food packaging, followed by film packaging.

Monitoring the plastic flows from the REMA 1000 store is currently reliant on waste composition studies. If done regularly, those can form a valid picture of waste generation and its composition. However, performing regular waste composition analysis is time consuming and does not have the potential to present real-time data. A monitoring technological system would have more value in large store set-ups. The systems could be linked to dashboards to show the results of the sorting efforts and raise awareness of employees and customers.

Intervention 2: Plastic in Healthcare

Summary of the intervention

After performing the analysis of the plastic consumption in Vejle in Deliverable D3.2 it was highlighted that public institutions, despite not having the highest stream in the city, have the capability to implement circular practices through public procurement and protocols that can then be replicated by other actors.

The second use case selected by the Vejle pilot refers to the public elderly home Sofiegården. The pilot has implemented a Mobile Sorting Unit to divert plastic from incineration. The solution enables staff in care facilities, including nursing homes, to sort plastic waste directly on site while performing other tasks. The Unit has the potential to significantly increase correct sorting and thereby, reduce the amount of plastic waste found in general waste that is subsequently being incinerated. The device is based on a design developed within the REFLOW project in collaboration with the private product design firm, Creos Design. Besides scaling potentials in healthcare centres, the waste in Vejle also sees potential in scaling this solution to other institutions in the Municipality, such as in schools and daycare centres.

In this use case, combined with the physical implementation, the pilot city chose to combine the inputs on circular procurement received from WP4 with the information and knowledge gathered from the pilot's local stakeholders, leading to the development of more than 10 procurement policy recommendations given to the municipality and their procurement department. The Sofiegården is considered as a significant benchmark where the examples collected from the local test site were used to demonstrate the potential of circular procurement policy.

Throughout the REFLOW project, the test site has shown a significant reduction in the amount of plastic thrown away as mixed waste. Thanks to the Mobile Sorting Station, more than 92% of plastic was diverted to recycling, corresponding to 42 kg of plastic waste saved per week (Figure 31). Meanwhile, the pilot has explored how to minimise the waste of resources, starting with the case of diapers. The pilot looked into current procurement protocols to reduce the avoidable, discarded quantity of diapers.

The five-year goal

Within the above use case chosen by the Vejle pilot, the attainable goal to be achieved in five years focuses on the implementation of circularity-focused procurement practices (i.e. policy) for plastic-containing healthcare products in healthcare facilities in Vejle and to implement the Mobile Sorting Station at 17 other elderly centres in the city. The aim is for all non-avoidable plastic products to be used as efficiently as possible, be easily identified, and be diverted away from incineration.

Figure 31. Life-cycle stages of the Sofiegården use case.

Methodology

Baseline. For the Sofiegården use case, two waste composition studies were used to calculate the environmental impacts. The first one, performed before the implementation of the intervention in 2020, was used as a quantitative baseline of the quantity of waste found in the waste stream, which totalled 2.37 tonnes yearly. The baseline scenario implies that all of the plastic is yearly sent to incineration in Romania. The second one, a two-week study performed within the scope of Deliverable 5.3, was used to complement the first one by determining the plastic composition, which highlighted that most of the plastic found in the waste stream at the Sofiegården institution is PP/PE, whereas another small portion represents PE film, PP film, and PET. The quantity and composition of the plastic waste allowed the calculation of end-of-life impacts (see Equation 1).

Equation 1.

$$\text{Total EOL impacts} = \sum (\text{Quantity of waste plastic}_n * \text{Impact plastic type}_n)$$

Table 16. Environmental impacts of plastic products End-of-Life stage (Source: Ecoinvent 3.8).

End-of-life treatment	End-of-life GHG emissions (tonnes CO ₂ -eq/tonne)	End-of-life human toxicity (tonnes 1,4 DCB-eq/tonne)
PP, PE, and PET recycling	0.36	0.12
PET incineration	2.03	0.26
PE/PP incineration	2.78	0.52
PE film incineration	3.02	0.57
PP film incineration	2.55	0.48
Other plastics incineration	2.53	0.44

For the Sofiegården use case, two waste composition studies were used to calculate the For the other plastics, an average of the environmental impacts of all the plastics found in the waste was made.

Intervention. The Vejle pilot has performed another waste composition study after the implementation of the REFLOW protocol. A diminution of plastic of about 92%, or 2.18 tonnes, was observed in the waste stream, where most of the plastic diverted consisted of PE film (31%), and hard plastics (PE, PP, and PET)(69%). The end-of-life impacts were calculated for both the plastics collected for recycling and for the one remaining in the mixed waste (see Equation 2).

Equation 2.

$$\text{Total EOL impacts} = \sum(\text{Quantity of waste plastic}(n) * \text{Impact plastic type}(n)) + \sum(\text{Quantity of recycled plastic}(n) * \text{Impact plastic type}(n))$$

Five-year scenario. With the intervention’s results, it was possible to determine the potential reduction of the scaled solution to the five-year goal set by the pilot (REFLOW Deliverable D5.3). In the next five-years, the pilot plans on applying this protocol at all the seventeen elderly centres in Vejle. The potential environmental impact reduction was simply calculated by proportionally scaling the impacts avoided during REFLOW for 2.18 tonnes collected yearly to a total of 37.13 tonnes within five-years.

Results

Baseline. Before the installation of the Mobile Sorting Station at Sofiegården, the 2.37 tonnes of plastic found in the waste stream were at the origin of the emission of 6.37 tonnes of CO₂-eq, and 1.15 tonnes of 1,4-DCB-eq.

Intervention. The analysis of the intervention yielded that recycling 2.18 tonnes of plastic previously incinerated from the Sofiegården elderly centre in Vejle helps avoid the emissions of about 5.16 tonnes of CO₂-eq. Additionally, about 0.82 tonnes 1,4-DCB are avoided which decreases the impacts of human toxicity near the end-of-life treatment infrastructures.

Five-year scenario. Within the next five years, the Vejle pilot wants to implement the protocol in the 17 elderly centres in the city. By proportionally scaling the environmental impacts avoided for the single elderly centre, it is possible to estimate the possibility of avoiding the emissions of about 87.72 tonnes of CO₂-eq during the plastic waste end-of-life treatments, as well as the use of emission of about 13.95 tonnes of 1,4-DCB.

The benefits of the intervention, both on the short- and long-term are highlighted below (see Table 17, Figure 32, and Figure 33).

Table 17. Comparison of the environmental impacts of the baseline and the intervention for the Plastic in Healthcare intervention.

Environmental impacts	Baseline	Baseline for scaled intervention	Intervention	Scaled intervention
Plastic incinerated (tonnes)	2.37	40.29	0.19	3.23
Plastic recycled (tonnes)	0	0	2.18	37.06
Total CO ₂ -eq emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	5.16	87.72
Total 1,4-DCB emissions avoided (tonnes)	0	0	0.82	13.95

Figure 32. Plastic waste comparison for Sofiegården.

Figure 33. GHG emissions comparison for Sofiegården.

Assumptions and limitations

The environmental impacts calculated for Sofiegården elderly centre were calculated based on multiple waste composition studies performed within REFLOW. In fact, the exact plastic composition of the plastic found in the waste stream and the one diverted were not measured during all composition studies, but rather an estimate was provided. Given a more detailed composition, the impacts associated would have been more specific, and specific products would have had better potential to be targeted for the implementation of alternatives.

Similarly, as for the REMA 1000 intervention, the scaling potential was based on the assumption that the elderly centres all had similar waste generation and recycling potential. Better baseline data would be needed for each centre to provide a more accurate estimate.

Discussion on scaling and barriers to market entry and resource monitoring

The public institutions involved in the pilot, including the Municipality of Vejle, have been a key leverage point to have a quick and direct positive impact on the city's environmental impacts. The Mobile Sorting Stations implemented at one elderly care centre allowed for the diversion of more than 90% of the plastics previously incinerated. Composed mostly of hard PP and PE products, the plastics were shown to present a high recyclability potential. The healthcare sector presents many barriers in terms of adopting circular practices, mainly due to health legislations and regulations in place. As opposed to the REMA 1000 use case where it would be key to quickly approach plastic alternatives and promote reuse, health care institutions, although they should also start evaluating these options, should put a maximum effort to properly sort the unavoidable single-use items currently in use. The high environmental impacts avoided within the REFLOW project is promising when evaluating the scaling potential across the urban metabolism. With its population ageing, the city should double-down on efforts to reduce the plastic waste in their healthcare institutions including, but not limited to, elderly centres.

The deployment of the Mobile Sorting Units at Sofiegården, similarly as for the recycling system implemented at REMA 1000 stores, would require a capacity-building effort across all healthcare institutions where implemented. The adequate sorting would be even more critical than for supermarkets as contaminated products can frequently be found in the waste streams of healthcare facilities. Before the implementation in multiple types of institutions, the regulations must be carefully investigated and addressed before allowing recycling.

Monitoring the resource flows represent a challenge as it requires the manual collection and characterisation of the waste stream. This process is highly time-consuming and comes with high costs. In the healthcare sector, the waste handled can often present potential risks for the handlers that should be avoided and be subjected to a high level of regulations. A technological solution to classify the waste should be prioritised, which would however consist of an important investment.

Material development research outputs

Alternative bio-based plastics

Developed in T3.2, the material development research has focused on biobased plastics for Vejle. The pilot's aim to reduce plastic waste also aligns with future developments of bio-based plastic at a local level. As part of Reflow, the pilot started raising awareness in their city about these options through a workshop on biomaterials. Furthermore, their partner Fablab Spinderihallerne⁵⁶ aims to develop a Bio Lab as part of their facilities for Vejle's citizens. In order to support these efforts, a [practical introduction to biomaterials](#) was developed as a slide deck. This resource seeks to support their educational activities and give some technical and practical guidelines on how to develop biomaterials. In addition, it was thought that this material would be theoretically complemented by the [Biomaterial Masterclass](#) designed for the Capacity Building section of the REFLOW platform.

⁵⁶ <https://www.spinderihallerne.dk/fablab/>

7. CONCLUSION

This report presents the environmental analysis of the REFLOW pilot cities' interventions and solutions developed throughout the project. The main objectives were to: calculate the direct environmental impacts of the chosen intervention on each pilot's urban metabolism and to clearly articulate the potential benefits of deploying the solution at a larger scale. Building on the detailed material flow analysis and the other methodologies developed within task T3.2 and T3.3, life-cycle thinking stands at the core of this approach and allows comparison with a baseline scenario before the beginning of the REFLOW interventions. From this analysis, it was demonstrated that the interventions have the potential to benefit each pilot's urban metabolism and can play a positive role in driving circularity within each of their cities. To support the future development of the intervention, this deliverable highlighted the few key challenges these interventions may face while they scale within their respective urban ecosystems.

Key takeaways and insights have emerged through these activities. To begin with, the variety of the environmental impact assessment conducted in this deliverable to adapt to the multiplicity of the types of interventions developed within REFLOW have illustrated that cities can effectively push towards the transition towards circularity from many perspectives. By and large, two main types of interventions were implemented by the pilots. Some pilots focused on optimising existent flows (e.g. in Milan with increasing food waste recovery, in Cluj with reducing electricity use, and in Vejle with increasing plastic recovery) to address current inefficiency within their urban metabolism, while other created new alternative resource flows (e.g. in Paris, Berlin, and Amsterdam) to provide another path than mainstream, business-as-usual resource flows. The analysis shows that either direction has merits and contributes in different ways to transform the urban metabolism of cities towards circularity.

A few reflections and takeaways can also be derived for future research on the environmental assessments of circular interventions. The variety of interventions led to methodological challenges since one single framework or methodology had difficulty adapting to the different types of data, time spans, system boundaries, and impacts that could be assessed. Nonetheless, a few takeaways can be generalised.

First, it is key to adopt a supply chain perspective, when data allows, to fully capture the life-cycle of products and services that are established by circular interventions. From there, the system boundaries can then be chosen, and it should be explicit what is or is not included, whether due to lack of data or trivial impact on the final results of the assessment. The system must also be defined within a specific time span. The modelling of mass or energy flows using mass or energy balance principles is then the second main step. It is indeed key to model the physical flows and their transformation within the established system boundaries to acquire an in-depth understanding of how an intervention affects the physical world.

Finally, the environmental impacts must be selected. This step is usually dictated both by data availability, the specific mass or energy flows modelled, and the overall scope and purpose of the assessment. Life-cycle databases are very useful for this step, although they often provide generic impact, which lacks the contextual information of the interventions. Thus, collecting as much data as possible and collecting insights from domain experts enable a more in-depth and refined analysis of the environmental impacts of the circular interventions. In terms of data collection for a wide range of solutions, it was possible to observe, in hindsight, that a more proactive approach would have yielded better results and insights in the environmental benefits of each intervention. From the planification of an intervention, a detailed monitoring plan for the baseline and intervention scenario should be established and operationalised beforehand. Approaching proactively the evaluation of the environmental performance of an intervention would be beneficial to resolve the timing difficulties encountered within a few use cases, where monitoring periods and testing periods were misaligned or established relatively late in the project. Most of the use cases analysed would have benefitted from a complete annual comparison to minimise the impacts of any outlying measurements (e.g. impact of seasonality) in their monitoring.

The difficulty to assess environmental impacts was also related to the very nature of the solutions developed in REFLOW. Milan Food Market 4.0⁵⁷ or Paris RE-Label⁵⁸ protocol are examples in which the environmental benefits could not be readily quantified, since they have only indirect impacts in terms of environmental performance. Nonetheless, their high potential could alter behaviours, facilitate tracking resources, and eventually minimise waste, thus resulting in indirect environmental impacts. The short-time frame and the absence of baseline monitoring did not allow for such quantification and assessment. The implementation of this type of solution could therefore later on be further quantified if a prior baseline is measured.

From the analysis, several logistics, monitoring, and financial trends have emerged from the evaluation of the barriers and challenges potentially faced by the REFLOW interventions in the future as they scale. For the pilots where the solutions implemented involved altering the resource flows in a circular manner within the urban metabolism (e.g. in Paris or Milan), physical spaces were often seen as a critical constraint to scale the circular activities. European cities are often limited in the availability of vacant (and affordable) spaces, which does not facilitate the temporary storage of resources for further reuse. As a result, early on in the process of such implementations, municipalities and local governing bodies should be approached to explore the possibilities of using vacant public spaces to promote circular and sustainable initiatives.

⁵⁷ <https://www.polifactory.polimi.it/en/polifactory/reflow/>

⁵⁸ <https://re-label.eu/>

As mentioned above, monitoring consisted of another key hurdle faced by many pilot interventions in the analysis of their respective environmental impacts. For all pilots, the iterative nature of their intervention has led to difficulties in collecting timely data in an ever-changing environment where baselines are difficult to define as long as the main characteristic of the intervention are not defined, and in setting a quantifiable five-year goal for scaling their interventions. The lack of data and subsequent monitoring can at times render difficult the analysis of the environmental benefits of the intervention. Ideally, monitoring would consist of a reliable consistent process in which frequent lectures are performed ensuring a representative portrait of the reality. An additional challenge was the pilots' ability to have enough capacity to ensure rigorous monitoring. To remediate the reliance on available capacity, technological monitoring solutions such as the Dimension-use developed by the Paris pilot or BOTTO developed by the Milan pilot should improve the monitoring of future intervention through a more standardised data collection protocol.

The last challenge revolves around the costs of scaling these interventions. Cities often have limited financial resources to effectively expand their developed solution at a scale where they could achieve the large-scale environmental benefits analysed above. Thus, access to seed financing and the development of the circular business models attached to each intervention are critical for their future success.

Each REFLOW pilot demonstrated the potential of its interventions in having a positive effect on their urban metabolism. The interventions currently being implemented represent only the beginning of what is possible in each city. Thanks to the tools, knowledge, and insights developed throughout the activities of Work Package 3 Circular Engineering, each pilot is equipped to scale their work over the years after the project. The pilots can ensure the presence of the quantifiable and measurable Circular Indicators developed within Task 3.1 and presented in Deliverable 3.1 to monitor their portfolio of interventions, for which a five-year target has been developed as part of Deliverable 5.3. (Task 5.3).

Adequate monitoring indicators provide clear targets to the pilot to identify any further avenues for improvement and to validate the benefits achieved with their current and future interventions. Thanks to the urban metabolism analyses and the strategic directions developed in Deliverable 3.2 (Task 3.3), the pilots have access to a solid understanding of the current state of their urban systems, and to a portfolio of future interventions that could be implemented to further their work after the project has ended.

The urban metabolism analysis methodology will be also a useful asset to guide further research on novel interventions to transition a city's metabolism towards circularity. The palette of biobased materials developed in Task 3.2 provide alternatives to impactful technical materials, and therefore new avenues for circular products that improve their urban metabolism. Finally, the environmental impact analysis performed in Task 3.4 and presented in this deliverable, provide critical information on the benefits and drawbacks of each REFLOW intervention, and can inform future improvements in the design of the current and future circular interventions. As a result of the work performed in each REFLOW task of Work Pack 3, the pilots have therefore acquired a toolkit to support them in reducing the environmental impact of their urban activities by fundamentally transitioning their urban system towards circularity.

REFERENCES

Literature

- Barber, A., & Pellow, G. (2006, November). LCA: New Zealand merino wool total energy use. In 5th Australian Life Cycle Assessment Society (ALCAS) conference, Melbourne (pp. 22-24).
- Beton A, Dias D, Farrant L, Gibon T, Le Guern Y, Desaxce M, Perwuelz A, Boufateh I. (2014) Environmental Improvement Potential of textiles (IMPRO Textiles). EUR 26316. Luxembourg (Luxembourg): Publications Office of the European Union; JRC85895
- Chapagain A. K., & Hoekstra, A. Y. (2008). The global component of freshwater demand and supply: an assessment of virtual water flows between nations as a result of trade in agricultural and industrial products. *Water international*, 33(1), 19-32.
- Coudard, Cobin, de Koning, Tukker, Mogollón I. (2021). Global water and energy losses from consumer avoidable food waste.
- Eurocities Environmental Forum (2019) Tackling the problem of plastic pollution in cities. https://nws.eurocities.eu/MediaShell/media/EUROCITIES_EEF_Followup.pdf
- Hogeboom, R. J., & Hoekstra, A. Y. (2017). Water and land footprints and economic productivity as factors in local crop choice: the case of silk in Malawi. *Water*, 9(10), 802.
- Kalliala, E. M., & Nousiainen, P. (1999). Environmental profile of cotton and polyester-cotton fabrics. *AUTEX Research Journal*, 1(1), 8-20.
- Koffi, B., Duerr, A., Iancu, A., Kona, A., & Janssens-Maenhout, G. (2017). CoM Default Emission Factors for the Member States of the European Union - Version 2017 - Data Europa EU, from <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets/jrc-com-ef-comw-ef-2017?locale=en>.
- Laursen, S. E., Hansen, J., Bagh, J., Jensen, O. K., & Werther, I. (1997). Environmental Assessment of Textiles. Life Cycle Screening of Textiles Containing Cotton, Wool, Viscose, Polyester or Acrylic Fibres. MILJOPROJEKT, 369.
- Lee, K. Y., & Ha, W. S. (1999). DSC studies on bound water in silk fibroin/S-carboxymethyl keratine blend films. *Polymer*, 40(14), 4131-4134.
- Rinaudo, M. (2006). Chitin and chitosan: Properties and applications. *Progress in Polymer Science*, Volume 31, Issue 7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2006.06.001>.
- Shen, L., & Patel, M. K. (2008). Life cycle assessment of polysaccharide materials: a review. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 16(2), 154-167.
- Turley, D. B., Horne, M., Blackburn, R. S., Stott, E., Laybourn, S. R., Copeland, J. E., & Harwood, J. (2009). The role and business case for existing and emerging fibres in sustainable clothing: final report to the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra), London, UK.
- Water Footprint Network . (2017). Water footprint of crop and animal products: a comparison. S/data. Disponível em: <<http://waterfootprint.org/en/water-footprint/product-waterfootprint/water-footprint-crop-and-animal-products/>>. Acesso em, 14.

- Van den Berghe A.J. & Zimmer, C. (2011). LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENTS OF SINGLE- VERSUS MULTIPLE-USE SURGICAL GOWNS
- Van der Werf, H. M., & Turunen, L. (2008). The environmental impacts of the production of hemp and flax textile yarn. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 27(1), 1-10.
- Velthuis, H.,J.,E.. (2020) Optimal design and operation of a solar thermal collector field in combination with low-temperature aquifer thermal energy storage to provide heat to a district heating network. <https://research.tue.nl/en/studentTheses/optimal-design-and-operation-of-a-solar-thermal-collector-field-i>
- Yilmaz, B., Yurdusev, M. A., & Harmancioglu, N. B. (2009). The assessment of irrigation efficiency in Buyuk Menderes Basin. *Water resources management*, 23(6), 1081-1095.

Databases and Datasets

- Ecoinvent 3.8 (2022): Wernet, G., Bauer, C., Steubing, B., Reinhard, J., Moreno-Ruiz, E., and Weidema, B., (2016). The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, [online] 21(9), pp.1218–1230. Available at: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8> > <https://ecoinvent.org/the-ecoinvent-database/>
- RIVM (2020) Milieubelasting van voedingsmiddelen | RIVM. <https://www.rivm.nl/voedsel-en-voeding/duurzaam-voedsel/database-milieubelasting-voedingsmiddelen>
- U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA). (2021). Dataset. <https://www.eia.gov/international/overview/world>

Websites

- Aries Transilvania (2022). <https://aries-transilvania.ro/>
- Associazione RECUP. (2022). <https://associazionerecup.org/>
- Berliner Wasserbetriebe. (2022) <https://www.bwb.de/de/index.php>
- BMA Techne - Amsterdam Economic Board. (2022) <https://amsterdameconomicboard.com/samenwerkingspartner/bma-techne/>
- Centrinno (2022). <https://centrinno.eu/>
- City of Amsterdam (2022). <https://www.amsterdam.nl/en/>
- CleanLease (2022). <https://nl.cleanlease.com/nl/home>
- Cordaan. (2022) <https://www.cordaan.nl>
- Croce Rossa Italiana. (2022). <https://cri.it/>
- DEN GAMLE GAARD. (2022). <http://www.dengamlegaard-stubberup.dk/>
- Denim Deal. (2022) <https://www.houseofdenim.org/denim-deal>
- Dress for Success. (2022). <https://dressforsuccess.org>
- Driven by Volumes. (2022) <https://drivenbyvolumes.io/>
- FabLab - Spinderihallerne. (2022) <https://www.spinderihallerne.dk/fablab/>
- Food Market 4.0 | REFLOW - Polifactory. (2022) <https://www.polifactory.polimi.it/en/polifactory/reflow/>

- Fraunhofer FOKUS. (2022) <https://www.fokus.fraunhofer.de/en>
- I:CO. (2022) <https://www.ico-spirit.com/en/>
- I-did. (2022) <https://www.i-did.nl>
- INCDTIM. (2022) <http://ro.itim-cj.ro/>
- Joint Research Centre | European Commission. (2022) https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/joint-research-centre_en
- Knowledge Hub – REFLOW. (2022) <https://reflowproject.eu/knowledge-hub/>
- Maison&Objet. (2022) <https://www.maison-objet.com/en/paris>
- Makers Unite. (2022) <https://makersunite.eu>
- MCS Datalabs. (2022) <https://mcs-datalabs.com/>
- OLVG. (2022) <https://www.olvg.nl>
- Opendot - Milano. (2022) <https://www.opendotlab.it/>
- Pakhuis de Zwijger. (2022) <https://www.dezwijger.nl>
- Plejecenter Sofiegården. (2022) <https://sofiegaarden.vejle.dk/>
- Polifactory. (2022) <https://www.polifactory.polimi.it/en/>
- Politecnico di Milano. (2022) <https://www.polimi.it/en/>
- Primăria Cluj-Napoca. (2022) <https://primariaclujnapoca.ro/>
- Prototypes for Europe eV. (2022) <https://www.prototypes.berlin/>
- Re-Label. (2022) <https://re-label.eu/>
- Rema 1000. (2022) <https://rema1000.dk/>
- Sogemi Spa. (2022) <https://www.sogemispa.it/>
- Valdelia. (2022) <https://www.valdelia.org/>
- Waag. (2022) <https://waag.org>
- WAO – Architecture. (2022) <https://wao.paris/>
- Waste Heat Valorisation: Improving energy efficiency in process industries | Results Pack | CORDIS | European Commission. (2022) <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/422033-waste-heat-valorisation>
- WeMake. (2022) <https://wemake.cc/>

APPENDIX

Table 18. GHG emissions of cotton mechanical recycling based on the Dutch Energy Grid.

Energy use during mechanical recycling (Source: Anton Luiken)	
0.5 kWh/kg	
Dutch grid carbon intensity (Source:Klimaatmonitor)	
516 CO ₂ eq-g/kWh	

Table 19. Products recovered by RECUP during the test period.

Products (Italian)	Products (English)	Kg	Products (Italian)	Products (English)	Kg
Carciofi	Artichokes	1,447.8	Meloni	Melons	220
Cime di rapa	Turnip	441.2	Verza	Cabbage	215
Sedano	Celery	390.5	Carote	Carrots	202.7
Cavolo Romano	Roman cabbage	652	Bergamotto	Bergamot	182
Cachi	Persimmons	569	Cavolo romanesco	Roman cabbage	171
Mele ruggine	Rust apples	363	Broccoli custoza	Broccoli custoza	162
Peperoni	Peppers	325	Cavolo riccio	Kale	160
Banane	Banana	311.5	Cavolo Nero	Black cabbage	156
Patate colli	Colli potatoes	296	Cipolle	Onions	154
Bietole	Chard	276	Mandarini	Mandarins	148
Puntarelle	Chicory	272	Mele rosse	Red apples	130

Products (Italian)	Products (English)	Kg	Products (Italian)	Products (English)	Kg
Pere	Pears	120	Uva	Grapes	35
Porro	Leeks	119	Pomodori	Tomatoes	35
Broccolo torbole	Torbole Broccoli	109	Pompelmi	Grapefruits	34
Insalata	Salad	107	Ravanelli	Radishes	25.5
Cavoletti Bruxelles	Brussels sprouts	102	Arance	Oranges	24
Patate	Potatoes	86	Mele	Apples	23.5
Coste	Chard	82.5	Melanzane	Eggplant	16
Patate sacchi	Sacchi potatoes	60	Broccoli	Broccoli	15
Kiwi	Kiwi	57	Cime	Brocoletto	12.4
Cipollotti	Onion	55	Cavolfiore	Cauliflower	10
Cicorie	Chicory	54	Melograno	Pomegranate	8
Clementine	Clementines	48	Scalogna	Shallots	5
Erbette	Herbs	48	Cipolla borretana	Onions	2
Zucchine	Zucchini	43.7	Fragole	Strawberries	2
Spinaci	Spinach	40.5	Insalatina	Salad	0.8
Cavolini bruxelles	Brussels sprouts	38.5	Spinacino	Spinach	0.8
Barbabietole	Beet	38			

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

Constructive metabolic processes for material flows in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.*